

Agrometeorology of Rapeseed-Mustard in Himachal Pradesh state of India

Rajendra Prasad, P.Vijaya Kumar, Ch. Srinivasa Rao

**CSK HPKV, Palampur, HP
and
Central Research Institute for Dryland
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FOREWORD

India is the largest rapeseed-mustard growing country in the world occupying first position in area and second in production. Indian mustard is nutritionally very rich and its oil content varies from 37 to 49%. As per ICAR vision document 2020, country's estimated need of oilseeds is 58 million tonnes. The current production of 6.2 million tonnes from 5.6 million ha area with 1.1 ton productivity is far below the achievable average of 2.0 tons/ha in mustard. The rapeseed oil production increased to 2.11 million tonnes in 2015-16 from the previous harvest of 1.94 million tonnes in 2014-15. Yet there is a huge gap between estimated need and production of edible oils in the country. Per capita oil consumption in India per year is 14.4 kg which is much lower than global average of 24 kg. As edible oil consumption is much more income-elastic, oilseeds production in India would be required to step up faster to keep pace with the consumption requirements. Cheap and adequate availability of edible oils is possible only if more area is brought under improved varieties and the yield gaps are bridged up through improved management practices. Rapeseed-mustard group of crop (s) are grown as sole crop or as an intercrop with wheat in Himachal Pradesh. This crop is grown over an area of 11.37 thousand ha with a total production of 6.37 thousand tonnes and productivity of 590 kg/ha which is much lower than national average. The lower productivity is thus, a major cause of concern. Deficit precipitation further aggregates the situation as was the case during last two monsoon seasons.

The climate and soils of the state are largely suitable for the cultivation of rapeseed-mustard. This crop is grown in almost all the districts mostly under rain fed conditions with some area in Kinnaur and Lahaul & Spiti also. Adequate residual moisture availability during sowing of rapeseed-mustard (particularly *toria*) ensures germination but inadequate and erratically distributed rains cause moisture stress at later stages which reduces the productivity. Shallow coarse textured soils with undulating topography have poor soil moisture holding capacity leading to poor moisture availability. Mid and high hills encounter low air and soil temperature conditions resulting in stunted growth during initial phases of crop growth. Therefore, weather takes a heavy toll on this crop. Ample work on the Agrometeorological aspect of rapeseed-mustard has been carried out under All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology, Palampur Centre. The documentation of this work will really be helpful to identify the critical gaps to plan the future research programmes and address the issues of sustainable production of rapeseed-mustard through adequate weather proofing strategies.

I congratulate authors for bringing out 'The Agrometeorology of Rapeseed-Mustard in Himachal Pradesh state of India'. I sincerely hope that this publication will be of immense use to the researchers, farm managers and the students.

Prof. Ashok Kumar Sarial
Vice-Chancellor

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Origin and history

The origin of word 'rape' is not known but most likely it came from 'rapa' a Latin word for turnip. The word 'rapeseed' is used to describe crop plants that meets the food quality standards of oils extracted from these plants. The English name, mustard, is derived from the Latin word 'mustum' or 'must' which is the expressed juice of grapes and ardens meaning hot or burning. There is a wide spectrum of wild species mentioned in family Brassicaceae and at present 63 cytodemes (crossing groups) of both diploid and tetraploid species are recognized. The vernacular name 'Sarson' is the derivative of Sanskrit word 'Sarshap' referred to the oil of mustard mentioned in Chandogya Upanishad (1000 BC). The three types of mustard were mentioned in the Sanskrit literature viz., 'Siddharth' for yellow sarson, 'Rajika' for brown sarson and 'Svet Sarshap' for white seeded *Brassica alba*.

The word *Brassica* originated from the Bresic or Bresych, the celtic name for cabbage and a contraction of praesecare (to cut off early) since the leaves were removed for fodder (Misra, 2005).

Historically, the *Brassicacae* are one of the earliest domesticated crop plants by man. It is mentioned in several ancient scriptures and believed that they might have been cultivated as early as 5000 BC. Seeds of mustard were found in the Channhu-daro of Harrapan civilization ca. 2300-1750 BC. In the literature, the word *Brassicacae* denotes for rapeseed, mustard, canola and wild / weedy relatives belonging to the family Brassicaceae (syn. cruciferae) and are not specific to a single species.

1.2 Importance of the crop

Rapeseed-mustard crops are one of the economically important agricultural commodities. The *Brassica* crops encompass many diverse types of plants, which are grown as vegetables, fodder or sources of cooking and burning oils and condiments. The seeds and leaves of rapeseed-mustard have been utilized for their flavor, medicinal, and preservative value since time immemorial.

1.3 Adaptation and geographical distribution

A range of wild and weedy species related to crop *Brassicas* and possessing extensive genetic variability occur in the Mediterranean region- particularly in Spain and Morocco. Rapeseed-mustard, comprising seven different species viz., Indian mustard, toria, yellow sarson, brown sarson, gobhi sarson, karan rai and taramira are being cultivated in 53 countries spreading all over the globe. The major oilseed *Brassica* producing regions include China, Canada, the Indian sub-continent and northern Europe. Asia contributes around 59% of area under rapeseed-mustard and 49% of its production in the world. India is the world's third largest producer of rapeseed-mustard (after China and Canada) having an area of 6.8 m ha, and the crop is spreading over 23 states and union territories.

Indian mustard [*Brassica juncea* (L.) Czernj & Cosson] is predominantly cultivated in Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Madhya Pradesh and Gujarat. It is also grown under some non-traditional areas of South India including Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. The crop can be raised well under both irrigated and rain fed conditions. Brown sarson (*Brassica campestris*) has 2 ecotypes; lotni and toria. Yellow sarson (*B. rapa* var. *trilocularis*) is cultivated in Assam, Bihar, Odisha, and West Bengal as *rabi* crop. Toria is grown as a catch crop in Punjab, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, and Himachal Pradesh. Taramira (*Eruca sativa* L.) is grown in the drier parts of North-West India comprising the states of Rajasthan, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh. Gobhi sarson (*B. napus* L. spp. *Oleferia* DC. var *annua* L.) and karan rai (*Brassica carinata* A. Braun) are the new emerging oilseed crops having limited area of cultivation. Gobhi sarson is a long duration crop confined to Haryana, Punjab and Himachal Pradesh. It has good yield potential, wider adaptability and possesses high quality oil. Karan rai with good yields and better rain fed adaptation, has advantage of substantial tolerance to pests and diseases and is also less prone to hailstorm and bird damage.

In Himachal Pradesh, rapeseed-mustard as a group of crops is grown over an area of 9.0 thousand ha with a total production of 2.4 thousand tonnes and productivity 267 kg/ha (Anonymous, 2012). Based upon the average data over the past ten years (1998-99 to 2007-08), rapeseed-mustard have accounted for 59.8% area under total oilseeds and contributed about 63.8% to the total oilseeds production in the state. These crops are grown from foot hills to high mountain areas of the state like Pangi, Dodrakwar, Kinnaur and Lahaul and Spiti. *Brassica* crops are grown both as pure as well as mixed crops with wheat. Local land races especially that of brown and yellow sarson are yet prevalent with the farmers due to their

early maturity though, these are low yielders and susceptible to diseases (Table 1.1). These crops are also grown in orchards to attract the bees for effective cross pollination (Thakur *et. at.*, 2007).

Table 1.1 Brassica group of crops grown in Himachal Pradesh

Sr. No.	Name of crop	Technical name	Major areas of cultivation
1.	Toria	<i>Brassica rapa</i> var. toria	Kangra, Una, Hamirpur, Sirmaur, Mandi and Bilaspur districts
2.	Brown sarson	<i>B. rapa</i> var. brown sarson	Cultivated as sole/mix crops in all the districts
3.	Yellow sarson	<i>B. rapa</i> var. yellow sarson	Pockets of Kangra (Khundian area), Mandi, Chamba and Hamirpur districts
4.	Mustard (raya) or brown mustard	<i>B. juncea</i> L.	All low and mid hills of the state
5.	Gobhi sarson	<i>B. napus</i> L.	Mainly Kangra, Una, Hamirpur and Mandi districts
6.	Karan rai	<i>B. carinata</i> L.	A new crop of rain fed areas of Una, Hamirpur and Kangra districts
7.	Taramira	<i>Eruca sativa</i> L.	Kangra, Una, Hamirpur, Solan and Sirmaur districts
8.	Banarsi rai or black mustard	<i>B. nigra</i> L.	Grown as mixture in linseed fields (Utera system) in Kangra and Mandi districts

1.4 Difference between rapeseed-mustard

Rapeseed -mustard group of crops belong to Cruciferae family and genus *Brassica*. Rapeseed is locally called as sarson, toria, whereas, mustard is called as raya / rai or laha. Though, rapeseed-mustard belong to the same family and genus, yet they differ with respect to their plant characteristics. Rapeseed is a herbaceous annual plant and the stems are generally covered with waxy deposit. Rapeseed plants are easily distinguished from mustard plants by the character of leaves. In rapeseed, the leaves are sessile, glabrous and hairy. The lower part of the blade (lamina) grasps the stalk partially or completely. Siliquae (pods) are thicker than those of mustard and are laterally compressed with a beak, one third to half of their length. Seeds are either yellow or brown with a smooth seed coat.

In mustard, plants are tall, erect and much branched. The leaves are not dilated at the base and clasping as in the case of rapeseed but are broad and pinnate. The siliquae are slender and erect with short and stout beaks. The colour of the seed is yellow, brown or dark brown with rough seed coat.

Winter and summer types of rape (*Brassica napus*) as well as turnip rape are physiologically different, the winter type does not come into the generative phase (seed

formation) if the crop has not been exposed to sub- zero temperature at early crop growth stages (Singh, 2005).

The crops covered under rapeseed are brown sarson, yellow sarson, toria, taramira, gobhi sarson and mustard includes, Indian mustard, Ethiopian mustard and black mustard.

1.5 Climatic and soil requirement

Oleiferous Brassicas are well adapted to cool and semi-moist growing conditions. They are cultivated as winter season crops in sub- tropics and as winter annuals in the milder regions of the temperate zones. At higher elevations and at the extremities of the temperate regions, they are grown as spring-sown crops. These crops can be successfully grown on variety of soils.

1.5.1 Climate

Rapeseed-mustard are basically temperate crops. Like any other crop, climate plays a very important role in growth and development of these crops also. Due to the climatic fluctuations, only 10 to 50 per cent of flowers develop into siliquae. Rapeseed-mustard crops have a wide photoperiodic range. They can be cultivated above the polar circles where there is 24 hours day light during summer months and day length less than 10 hours during winter. Indian cultivars are generally grown within 10-13 hours daylight. These crops require high temperature for the completion of vegetative phase and cool weather and clear sky during reproductive phase for better development of oil. Higher temperature during early growth stage results in higher leaf area index leading to vigorous growth, higher formation of branches and consequently stronger reproductive growth phase. Under high humidity and cloudy weather conditions, incidence of diseases and pests is higher (Kumar, 2005).

There is a specific temperature range required for its growth and development. Under optimum temperature, seeds show the highest percentage of germination and the shortest germination period as well. The temperature range of 0.5-3°C, 20-35°C and 35-40°C can be considered to be minimum, optimum and maximum, respectively (Thakur *et. al.*, 2007). Little plant growth occurs when the temperature is below 5°C and soil temperature is low after germination and early leaf development. Higher temperature, maximum (30-32°C) and minimum (20-22°C) during early growth stages results in vigorous growth, higher leaf area index, and consequently stronger reproductive phase. The low soil temperature reduces the water and nutrient adsorption by seedling roots and increases the vulnerability to insect-pests,

diseases and injury resulting in poor seed yields. In general, toria can germinate well at higher temperature (35°C) than mustard. In the absence of honeybees and other fertilizing agents, the yield is highly reduced. Cloudy weather during flowering adversely affects the honey bee activities, and hence, reduces the pollination, resulting in poor yields.

In India, this group of crop(s) are grown during *rabi* season from September/October to February/March/April. These crops grow well in areas having 25-40 cm rainfall during the season (Rathore and Kumpawat, 1992).

1.5.2 Soil

Rapeseed-mustard crops thrive well on a wide variety of soils, but perform well on loamy soils having pH around 7. However, the crops can yield well at soil reaction ranging from 6.5 to 8.3. Rapeseed could be grown successfully on light textured soils provided moisture and fertility are adequate. These crops cannot tolerate waterlogged conditions hence, drainage may be required on heavy soils. In the drier areas, higher moisture holding clays and clay loam soil also give good returns (Kumar, 2005).

About 35.2% of the area of Himachal Pradesh has medium deep (50-100 cm) soils followed by 18.0% shallow (50 cm). Afforestation with coniferous species on high altitudes and deciduous species on mid and lower altitudes, graded bunding with plantation of climatically adapted fruit crops along contours and cultivation of *Kharif* millets suggested for soils having shallow to medium depth. About 17.9% area is covered with deep soils (100 cm) which is suitable for growing wheat, maize and rice.

Whether the climate and soils of entire state are highly suitable for rapeseed-mustard or not, but due to the advantage of wider adaptability, these crops are grown in almost all the districts of the state. The main districts are Kangra, Mandi, Hamirpur, Una, Sirmaur, Bilaspur, Shimla, Solan, Kullu and Chamba which account for over 99% area and production under rapeseed-mustard.

CHAPTER 2

Agro-climatic characteristics

Characterization of crop growing environment is a pre-requisite in crop planning and evolving strategies to overcome climate/weather induced changes in the meso/micro climate. Anomalies in climate variables need to be properly understood to make agricultural sector resilient. Thus, historic data on climatic variables was analysed using appropriate statistical tools [produced by NARS, National Agriculture Research System] and Weathercock 15 of CRIDA (Central Research Institute of Dryland Agriculture) enabling the development of location specific technologies/adaptive strategies. The analysis carried out by AICRPAM, Palampur centre on the agro-climatic characterization of mustard growing environments is reported hereunder:

2.1 Normal weekly temperature and rainfall

Normal weekly maximum and minimum temperature for nine locations representing different agroclimatic zones of the state, viz., Akrot, Bajaura, Berthin, Dhaulakuan, Kangra, Malan, Palampur, Salooni and Shimla have been reported in Annexure 1. The maximum temperature varied between 11.6 (Shimla) to 37.0°C (Akrot) and minimum temperature varied between 0.3 (Bajaura) to 21.1°C (Akrot).

Normal weekly rainfall and rainy days for 40 stations are given in Annexure 1a & 1b. The rainfall varied between 0.0 (Chachiot) to 45.5 mm (Nurpur). The rainy days varied between 0 to 1 day per week.

2.2 Normal monthly temperature and rainfall

Regarding temperature averages during different months, the mean maximum temperature as an average of nine stations (31.6°C) is observed to be highest during May and lowest (17.1°C) during January (Annexure 1c). April and May months are the warmest at all the nine stations of the state. Location-wise, Akrot in district Una was the warmest location (37.8°C) followed by Dhaulakuan in Sirmaur district (36.9°C) and Berthin in Bilaspur district (35.6°C). Salooni and Shimla are the cooler locations (21.1 to 25.0°C) as far as the maximum temperature is concerned.

Among the months, January was the coolest month (4.7°C) followed by December (5.8°C) and February (6.5°C) whereas the warmest month is May (16.8°C) followed by October (13.6°C) and April (13.0°C) (Annexure 1c). But temperatures are high at Salooni (8.1°C) and is lowest at Bajaura (1.0°C) followed by Berthin and Shimla (3.6°C). Information on the monthly rainfall at a location is helpful for crop planning, cultivar selection, run-off estimation, determining crop water needs, and for designing watersheds and ultimately irrigation system. The rainfall distribution on monthly basis with the associated variability for different stations is presented in Annexure 1d. November is the driest month in the state (18 mm) followed by October (30 mm), December (34 mm) and April (45 mm). However, difference in the rainfall of October and December is just of 4mm. One of the stations, Salooni receives highest *rabi* season rainfall during October to April (95 to 198 mm).

Therefore, it is not the total amount of rainfall on a monthly basis that is vital, but the number of rainy days in a month determines the distribution of rain, this is what matters the most. High variability in rainfall is norm rather than exception. District-wise average number of rainy days on a monthly basis are furnished in the Annexure 1e. It may be observed that lowest frequency is noticed during November (1 day) followed by October and December (2 days each). The months of January, April and May have same frequencies (4 days) and February and March (5 days). Amongst the stations, most of the stations showed similar number of rainy days during the months of November and December. Twenty four stations showed single rainy day during November whereas rest of the stations witnessed 2 to 5 rainy days. Rainfall during *rabi* season is generally substantial and on an average the state receives 395 mm rainfall in 27 days.

2.3 Moisture and temperature at sowing and critical stages

The largest quantities of best rapeseed-mustard are produced in areas favoured with cool and moist weather during a fairly long growing period followed by a dry and warm weather to enable the siliquae to ripen properly. Although these crops are resistant to moisture stress, *Eruca stavia* followed by *Brassica carinata* and *Brassica juncea* are more tolerant to moisture stress than the rapeseed. Moisture stress at critical growth stages (flowering and siliquae filling) reduces the seed filling, seed size and oil content. The water requirement 450 mm is the most desirable for the crop. The crop is vulnerable to diseases and insect-pests when there is severe moisture stress (Kumar, 2005). The high temperatures and

absence of rains during flowering period decreases seed yields. This combination also disrupts the biosynthesis of fat and fatty acid content in the seeds (Mavi, 1994).

2.4 Crop growing environment

All efforts to obtain profitable crop production involve improving adaptations of either crop to the environment or environment to the crop. Agro-meteorology of the crop primarily aims to select/ characterize the efficient crop growing environments and also attempts to weather-wise management of crop(s) for higher productivity. Detailed weather-wise crop management of rapeseed-mustard growing environments is given in Annexure 2. The resultant effect of genotype environment management interaction is actual harvested productivity which may be half to one third of the potential yield. The actual productivity under field conditions is influenced by host of unpredictable factors. Proper knowledge of plant growth characteristics, factors affecting growth and their relationships is essential for any substantial success in crop production technology.

The main components of the crop growing environment, which govern the spread and production of these crops during a season are soil moisture and temperature. The crop is sown with the onset of cooler temperatures in October with conserved soil moisture or pre-sowing irrigation depending upon the situation. When grown under rain fed condition, the available soil moisture mainly governs the growth and development of crop, which is highly variable. The adverse effect of temperature becomes more pronounced when it deviates from the optimum during vegetative and seed development phases. Since weather is an important determinant of seed yield in brassicas, hence it is imperative to know the range of crop growing environments in which the crops can be grown profitably and also to analyse the variability of production and productivity (Rao and Singh, 2005). Since much work in India has not been done more strenuous efforts are required in this direction.

2.5 Crop weather Calendar

The Crop Calendar is a tool that provides timely information about crop stage and condition of the crop. It contains information on planting, important phenophases and harvesting periods of locally adapted crops in specific agro-ecological zone or a district to be specific. Detailed information regarding crop phenology of variety HPN-3 was collected from the AICRPAM-Annual Progress Reports for five years (2010-11 to 2014-15). During this period, periodic field scouting and agro-climatic field surveys were also carried out to further

fine tune the phenology of this crop/variety. Accordingly, the crop weather calendar was designed. The specific details provided by the AICRPAM coordinating unit in a capacity building program on “Analysis of data collected in AICRPAM, crop weather relations and documentation of results etc.” organized at CRIDA, Hyderabad during 28th July to 06th Aug, 2015 were also included to come up with district-wise uniform crop weather calendar of this crop. After the successful emergence and under non-limiting input supplies, the crop growth phases are influenced by weather conditions *viz.*, ambient temperature, rainfall, relative humidity, BSS and radiation etc. The upper most portion of the calendar indicates the normal weather requirements during various weeks of the crop growth period (Fig. 2.1). The middle portion shows the duration of important growth phases like sowing and seedling establishment, vegetative phase, flowering phase, pod development and physiological maturity in weeks. These phenophases were completed in 5, 6, 8, 4 and 4 weeks, respectively. At the bottom, pest and diseases of the crop are shown with the duration of life cycle of the most important pest, mustard aphids along with its favourable weather conditions. This information on the weather parameters would be highly beneficial in issuing weather based agro advisories and warning of expected weather and its associated adverse effects on the crop.

The crop experiences 11.5-35.0°C and 2.5-18.5°C maximum and minimum temperature respectively, 20-90% relative humidity, 5-35 mm rainfall/week, 8-20 mm/week evaporation, 3-10 hrs/day bright sunshine hours and yielded 23.5 q/ ha at Palampur. Though, lot of experience and information has been used in preparation of this crop weather calendar, still additional information is required to be added for its regular updation, which can be done by regular recording of phenological data every year, otherwise information not recorded would be lost forever.

Fig 2.1 Crop Weather Calendar

Crop: Gobbi sarson

Duration: Long (170-190 days)

State: Himachal Pradesh

District: Kangra

Parameter	Std Week	October				November				December				January				February				March				April			
		42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	
Tmax (°C)		25	24	23	22	21	20	19	19	18	17	16	15	15	15	15	16	16	17	17	18	20	21	22	23	24	26	27	
Tmin (°C)		13	12	12	11	10	9	7	7	7	6	5	5	5	5	6	6	7	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15		
RHm (%)		61	62	59	59	58	57	60	56	58	58	61	61	63	63	63	63	64	61	60	57	58	56	56	51	50	50		
RHe (%)		47	47	46	47	45	45	47	45	49	48	50	51	50	54	51	50	54	53	49	48	45	47	47	45	41	39	39	
WS (kmph)		3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4		
WD		North easterly/west south westerly											Easterly north easterly/west south westerly						East north easterly/west south westerly										
BSS (hr/day)		8	8	8	7	7	7	7	6	6	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	5	6	6	6	6	6	7	7	8	7		
S. Rad (MJ/m ² /day)		37	33	33	28	34	40	30	37	24	25	28	25	30	25	25	22	25	26	27	23	24	32	33	35	31	41	35	
EVP (mm/week)		27	25	25	24	23	22	19	17	16	15	17	13	14	13	14	16	16	17	19	22	25	26	28	31	35	38	42	
Rain (mm/week)		6	3	3	4	4	3	6	4	12	9	19	16	20	20	31	16	26	36	25	28	19	27	31	15	15	13	13	
Rainy days/week		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1		
Phenophase Duration (days)		Sowing & seedling establishment (32-35)				Vegetative (40-42)				Flowering (50-55)				Siliquae filling (28-30)				Maturity (25-30)											
Tmax (°C)		14.5-26.5				12.0-22.0				11.5-22.5				14.5-30.5				26.0-35.0											
Tmin (°C)		6.0-12.0				2.5-9.5				2.5-10.5				6.5-15.5				13.5-18.5											
RHm (%)		70-90				50-80				60-90				40-80				30-70											
RHe (%)		30-65				30-70				30-80				20-70				20-50											
WS (kmph)		5.0-9.0				4.0-6.0				4.0-10.0				4.0-7.0				4.0-10.0											
WD		North easterly/west south westerly											Easterly north easterly/west south westerly						East north easterly/west south westerly										
BSS (hr/day)		6-8				6-9				3-6				5-7				5-10											
S. Rad (MJ/m ² /day)		28-37				24-45				17-33				23-33				31-41											
EVP (mm/week)		12-20				10-15				8-14				15-18				18-20											
Rain (mm/week)		8-10				5-10				25-30				30-35				5-10											
Rainy days/week		1				1				2				1				1											
Congenial weather for pest & disease		Mustard Aphids											T max 15.5-23.5°C T min 3.0-12.0°C RHm 52-85% RHe 36-72% BSS 1-9 hr/day																

**All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology,
CSK HPKV, PALAMPUR**

2.6 Spatio-temporal changes in area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard

In Himachal Pradesh, rapeseed-mustard is a major oilseed crop of *rabi* season covering an area of 9.1 thousand ha and production of 4.7 thousand t/ha (Anonymous, 2012). In addition, taramira (*Eruca sativa* L.) is also cultivated by the farmers on small scale, especially in mid and low hills, mainly being used as animal fodder and feed. The area under *rabi* oilseeds had increased from 1981-82 (6.3 thousand ha) to 1999-2000 (9.7 thousand ha). However after the year 1999-2000 the area remained stagnant up to 2013-14 (9.1 thousand ha). The productivity showed wide fluctuations over the years. The spatio-temporal changes in area and productivity were worked out using 33 years data (1981-82 to 2013-14) and are presented in Fig 2.2.

Fig 2.2 Area and productivity during 1981-82 to 2013-14

2.7 Climate change and variability during growing season

Climate variability refers to the climatic parameter of a region varying from its long-term mean. For example, some years have below average rainfall, some have average or above average rainfall. Generally no two years get the same amount of rainfall in a row. The actual rainfall varying from the mean presents drought and flood conditions. However, climate change is a change in the statistical distribution of weather patterns when that change lasts for an extended period of time at least few decades. India is becoming more vulnerable to climate change as extreme weather events are on rise and major portion of population derive their livelihoods from agriculture and allied sectors.

2.7.1 Role of minimum temperature in Himachal Pradesh during *rabi* season

Due to passage of western disturbances, the northern region of the country experiences wide range of temperature fluctuations during the *rabi* season. Minimum temperature is one of the parameters that had been identified as a key factor in determination of crop growth, yield variations and severity of pest/disease attack. Table 2.1 illustrates the variability of maximum and minimum temperatures at Palampur (November 5 to May 20), Malan, Bajaura and Shimla (November 11 to May 29) during *rabi* season (200 days each) for four seasons (2011-12 to 2014-15). Similar analysis was also carried out for two *rabi* seasons (1988-89 & 1989-90) in the Delhi region (IARI, New Delhi, 1992) during October 8 to March 31 (175 days). The results indicated that CV values of minimum temperature were highest followed by maximum temperature at all the stations studied. The coefficient of variation in minimum temperature for the entire season was found to be much higher (2-4 times) at these stations as compared to maximum temperature.

Table 2.1 Coefficient of variation (%) in temperature during *rabi* season

Period (days)	Palampur				Malan				Bajaura				Shimla			
	Maximum temperature															
	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15
01-20	4	5	6	4	4	20	3	3	5	12	6	7	10	12	8	6
21-40	10	18	7	9	8	6	8	27	13	24	9	38	13	24	13	33
41-60	6	12	11	15	26	7	6	9	23	17	25	19	35	16	26	14
61-80	27	15	17	21	11	13	8	15	23	28	22	19	37	26	20	33
81-100	13	15	15	16	11	11	11	12	23	32	35	29	23	32	37	16
101-120	17	23	24	21	11	12	9	18	22	25	22	22	13	25	23	29
121-140	16	10	16	18	13	9	14	13	14	21	23	23	19	18	18	18
141-160	7	14	12	16	12	6	5	18	16	10	14	19	14	8	11	19
161-180	7	9	15	10	6	10	6	6	12	10	13	6	9	12	9	8
181-200	6	20	8	9	2	12	3	7	17	17	16	13	7	13	9	9
Minimum temperature																
01-20	15	13	19	24	9	14	10	14	73	89	123	132	16	26	17	14
21-40	26	23	16	26	16	6	11	21	104	110	213	73	30	51	31	55
41-60	69	34	28	34	17	28	7	13	62	600	635	2351	81	69	66	35
61-80	62	65	44	32	16	18	14	14	68	1319	117	158	331	75	67	128
81-100	50	37	35	41	32	22	21	27	91	81	141	118	117	50	97	52
101-120	29	28	36	29	14	15	11	13	48	46	42	53	35	48	44	73
121-140	42	18	25	30	19	10	8	22	42	30	35	43	37	28	33	35
141-160	14	18	14	16	19	10	7	10	20	20	18	13	24	15	23	26
161-180	13	13	23	14	10	9	7	9	21	14	23	17	22	18	18	16
181-200	14	15	11	14	3	15	14	4	14	13	12	14	20	17	16	14

2.8 Stable rainfall period for rapeseed-mustard cultivation

The suitability of rapeseed-mustard crop varieties of different maturity durations at different locations *viz.*, Bajaura, Malan, Palampur and Shimla was examined using the rainfall data of 29, 15, 41 and 30 years for respective stations. For this, rainfall periods having weekly rainfall of 15 mm and 180% coefficient of variation of rainfall can be considered as ‘stable’ period.

From January 8 to May 6, a period of 119 days was identified as stable rainfall period for Palampur (Fig 2.3). The stable rainfall period was found to be 84 days (Jan 8- April 1) at Malan and 112 days (Jan 8 –April 29) each at Bajaura & Shimla (Table 2.2). The study revealed that for sowing and seedling establishment, if sufficient soil moisture is conserved through effective soil moisture conservation technologies, a good rapeseed-mustard crop can be raised even under rain fed conditions as rainfall probability is fairly high after January and later till flowering and siliquae development which declines thereafter. Similar analysis had also been attempted for crop planning for wheat in Kangra, Kullu and Shimla districts of Himachal Pradesh (Prasad *et. al.*, 2015).

Fig 2.3 Stable rainfall period for rapeseed-mustard cultivation at Palampur

Table 2.2 Stable rainfall period for rapeseed-mustard cultivation at different locations of Himachal Pradesh

Locations	Data base (years)	Stable rainfall period (days)
Palampur	41	08 Jan- 06 May (119)
Bajaura	29	08 Jan-29 April (112)
Malan	15	08 Jan- 01 April (84)
Shimla	30	08 Jan-29 April (112)

CHAPTER 3

Crop weather relationship

A comprehensive knowledge on physiological processes in crop plants such as photosynthesis, transpiration, growth and development which are influenced by the process of energy and mass exchange has led to the development of dynamic crop-growth models and these are increasingly applied to estimate crop yields at regional levels. At the same time, traditional empirical-statistical models continued to be developed to understand and quantify the role of weather variables in determining the crop productivity of a given location/region. Crop- weather relationship studies in rapeseed-mustard were started at Palampur Centre under All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology (AICRPAM) during 2003-04 and continued till 2011-12 with three rapeseed (gobhi sarson) varieties viz., HPN-1, HPN-3 & Hyola-401 under irrigated conditions. Two more varieties viz., ONK-1 and GSL-1 were added during 2012-13 and the experiment was continued till 2014-15. Data from the work carried out at this Centre and some data from All India Coordinated Rapeseed-Mustard Improvement Project in CSKHPKV were analysed and results are reported here-under:

3.1 Phenological stages and growing degree days

The role of temperature on phenology of five rapeseed (gobhi sarson) varieties grown under irrigated conditions was evaluated during *rabi* 2010-11 to 2013-14 at Palampur. Perusal of data on average number of days taken for completion of different phenological stages indicated that days taken decreased with delay in sowing in all varieties (Table 3.1). The varieties, HPN-1, HPN-3 and Hyola-401 took almost similar number of days for each phenological stage. These varieties also accumulated higher thermal time or growing degree days (GDD) similar to the pattern of number of days taken for completion of different phenophases (Table 3.2). Delay in sowing curtails the duration of all the varieties and also correspondingly reduce the growing day requirement. Duration from sowing to first flower was lowest in case of early sowing (20th October) and highest in normal sowing (30th October) in most of the varieties. However, GDD for sowing to occurrence of different phenological stages was highest in early sowing only. The reduction in duration under delayed sowing was more pronounced in post flowering stages. Photo-thermal units (PTU) and Heliothermal units (HTU) for all varieties under three sowing dates were also evaluated and presented in Annexure 3 & 3a.

Table 3.1 Days taken for completion of different phenological stages of varieties sown on different dates at Palampur

Phenological stages/ Sowing dates	Days taken to complete different Phenophases		
	20 th Oct	30 th Oct	10 th Nov
GSL-1			
Emergence	11	7	6
First flower	85	89	85
50% flowering	117	105	100
90% siliquae filling	165	148	139
Physiological maturity	181	163	153
HPN-1			
Emergence	8	13	12
First flower	85	101	100
50% flowering	117	115	116
90% siliquae filling	155	151	143
Physiological maturity	182	175	166
HPN-3			
Emergence	8	13	14
First flower	86	99	97
50% flowering	119	114	115
90% siliquae filling	153	147	141
Physiological maturity	182	175	166
Hyola-401			
Emergence	9	14	14
First flower	84	96	98
50% flowering	117	119	110
90% siliquae filling	153	143	143
Physiological maturity	182	176	168
ONK-1			
Emergence	4	13	12
First flower	72	96	90
50% flowering	109	115	108
90% siliquae filling	158	158	149
Physiological maturity	170	172	163
Pooled			
Emergence	8	12	12
First flower	82	96	94
50% flowering	116	114	110
90% siliquae filling	157	149	143
Physiological maturity	179	172	163

3.2 Models to predict phenophases

Regression equations were developed by relating GDD with number of days taken for completion of different phenological stages of three varieties viz., HPN-1, HPN-3 and Hyola-401 for the period of five years, 2009-10 to 2013-14 and two varieties viz., GSL-1 and ONK-1 for 2012-13 and 2013-14. The equations developed were tested with the independent data sets of 2014-15. The difference between observed and predicted days indicated that the model over-estimated the number of days for majority of the phenological stages (Table 3.3). The model could better predict the flowering stage than the

physiological maturity stage in all the varieties. Predictions are required to be fine-tuned with more accurate data recording on phenological events.

Table 3.2 Phenophase-wise accumulated growing degree days (GDD) taken by different varieties sown on different dates at Palampur

Phenological stages/ Sowing dates	GDD taken to complete different phenophases		
	20 th Oct	30 th Oct	10 th Nov
GSL-1			
Emergence	132	88	63
First flower	728	701	621
50% flowering	910	805	721
90% siliquae filling	1372	1231	1125
Physiological maturity	1576	1434	1317
HPN-1			
Emergence	111	145	136
First flower	746	753	675
50% flowering	942	848	807
90% siliquae filling	1257	1209	1119
Physiological maturity	1679	1603	1461
HPN-3			
Emergence	106	145	152
First flower	761	746	660
50% flowering	956	849	800
90% siliquae filling	1277	1141	1091
Physiological maturity	1682	1601	1503
Hyola-401			
Emergence	115	152	164
First flower	751	720	709
50% flowering	945	887	798
90% siliquae filling	1270	1093	1127
Physiological maturity	1677	1612	1508
ONK-1			
Emergence	148	137	115
First flower	695	724	632
50% flowering	905	841	740
90% siliquae filling	1373	1275	1174
Physiological maturity	1536	1475	1376
Pooled			
Emergence	122	133	126
First flower	736	729	659
50% flowering	932	846	773
90% siliquae filling	1310	1190	1127
Physiological maturity	1630	1545	1433

Table 3.3 Difference between observed and predicted days taken for completion of different phenophases

Phenological stages/ Sowing dates	Difference between observed and predicted days		
	20 th Oct	30 th Oct	10 th Nov
GSL-1			
Emergence	9	6	11
First flower	17	-5	3
50% flowering	-1	-9	0
90% siliquae filling	8	-2	11
Physiological maturity	15	6	21
HPN-1			
Emergence	9	15	20
First flower	17	-1	0
50% flowering	-12	-9	-8
90% siliquae filling	-16	-10	-6
Physiological maturity	18	21	24
HPN-3			
Emergence	9	16	21
First flower	19	1	-2
50% flowering	-3	-8	-6
90% siliquae filling	-13	-17	-10
Physiological maturity	19	22	24
Hyola-401			
Emergence	9	16	21
First flower	20	-2	1
50% flowering	4	-5	-4
90% siliquae filling	-12	5	-7
Physiological maturity	20	22	24
ONK-1			
Emergence	8	13	16
First flower	19	-2	-3
50% flowering	2	-5	-11
90% siliquae filling	3	7	5
Physiological maturity	11	16	16

3.3 Impact of temperature during *rabi*, 2004-05

The *rabi* crops are long day plants and are thermo-sensitive and prefer low temperature. The month of March in 2004 all over India and its neighbourhood was unusually warm. The main reason of abnormally high temperature was passage of less number of western disturbances. Rain spells during February were only three, against the average of 4-5. The dry conditions during March and the period up to April 20 (normally 4-5 rain spells observed in the state) caused the temperature to rise above 33°C. However, the average for the periods was 25°C (Prasad and Rana, 2006). The comparison of actual temperature record of CSK Himachal Pradesh Agricultural University Agrometeorological Observatory with normal indicated 8-10°C above normal temperature during second fortnight of March, 2004. In fact, summer was set in 20 days earlier than normal in Himachal Pradesh. The higher temperature coincided with reproductive phase of majority of the crops grown in the state.

Due to prevailing high temperature and drought-like situation, there were reports of major impact on different crops grown in the state. An attempt was made to study the effect of higher temperature on several crops including rapeseed-mustard.

Siliquae formation and their filling of HPN-1, HPN-3 and Hyola-401 was severely affected in rain fed low hills. Rise in temperature during March led to flower drop, empty siliquae in late sown *Brassica* spp. and forced maturity in normal sown crops. Compared to 2001-02, the average yield reduction during 2002-03 and 2003-04 was found to be 38.9 and 59.3%, respectively (Table 3.4). The reduction was 20% higher during 2003-04. The yield reduction during the corresponding period was considerably higher than wheat.

Table 3.4 Effects of high temperature during March on rapeseed-mustard grown during different seasons in mid hills of Himachal Pradesh

Months/Year	2002-03	2003-04	2004-05	2005-06
Productivity (kg/ha)	884	540	360	470
Percent decrease over 2001-02	-	-38.9	-59.3	-8.24

3.4 Performance under varied thermal environments

To understand the performance of rapeseed-mustard during different phenophases, the accumulated deviations of daily mean temperatures from normal for each fortnight of different months (October to April) were calculated over five years and presented in Table 3.5.

Growing season during 2013-14 was the warmer (+127.4°C) followed by 2014-15 (+44.3°C), 2012-13 (-46.8 °C), 2011-12 (-67.5 °C) and 2010-11 (-100.2 °C). Out of the five seasons studied, in three seasons i.e., 2013-14, 2012-13 and 2011-12, the average yield over all the varieties followed the pattern of higher positive deviations or lower negative deviations.

Moderate warming during second fortnight of February increased the yield considerably. Earlier studies in wheat suggest that warming during January, February and first fortnight of March had beneficial effect on wheat yield under mid hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh (Prasad *et. al.*, 2015).

Table 3.5 Accumulated deviations of mean temperature from normal for different fortnights of the growing of seasons of rapeseed-mustard at Palampur

Season/ Month/ fortnight	Accumulated deviations of temperature from normal (°C)														Average yield (kg/ha)	
	October		November		December		January		February		March		April			Over the season
	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II				
2010-11	-9.4	-9.0	-13.7	-19.9	+1.05	-10.5	-4.3	+16.0	-40.0	+23.1	-3.6	-54.2	+11.9	+12.3	-100.2	1532

2011-12	-6.9	-6.5	-17.0	-22.2	-25.1	-12.1	+11.3	+28.1	+20.4	-6.6	+9.8	-45.6	-26.8	+31.7	-67.5	934
2012-13	-5.2	+18.0	+6.4	+7.4	-13.4	-19.9	+0.3	-1.75	-13.7	+10.1	-34.8	-9.8	-10.9	+20.5	-46.8	1644
2013-14	-0.9	+1.7	+32.7	-1.7	-7.5	+11.5	+4.75	-13.3	+14.4	+14.2	+31.3	-3.3	+15.7	+27.8	+127.4	1802
2014-15	+4.6	+10.1	+5.3	-1.05	-4.05	+10.3	-9.5	+14.2	-5.1	-25.3	+28.3	-19.8	+32.2	+4.1	+44.3	1205

3.5 Effect of temperature on yield

3.5.1 During emergence and vegetative phases

Various crop growth phases experience variable temperature conditions under variable crop growing environments. Falling temperature during emergence and vegetative phase were found to be related with decrease in seed yield in gobhi sarson. Within the available data range, the average temperature of 19.8 °C and 14.4 °C during emergence and vegetative phases, were found to be optimum for obtaining higher yield under Palampur conditions (Fig. 3.1).

Fig. 3.1 Effect of temperature on yield during emergence and vegetative phases

3.5.2 During reproductive phase

The average duration of reproductive phase of four gobhi sarson varieties (HPN-1, Hyola-401, GSL-1 and ONK-1) varied from 74 to 49 days depending upon the time of sowing. The influence of temperature on this phase and yield of these varieties during 2010-11 to 2014-15 was studied. It was found from the results that maximum yield was realized during the years with mean maximum temperature prevailing in the range of 15.7°C to 17.2°C across the varieties tested (Fig 3.2). These temperatures could be considered as optimum for this phase. An increase in mean maximum temperature by 2 to 3°C from this optimum, resulted in drastic reduction of seed yield in all varieties, which was found to be higher in variety Hyola-401 (from 1732 kg to 784 kg i.e., 57.6%) and lowest in ONK-1 (from 1826 kg to 1296 kg i.e., 29%).

Fig 3.2 Effect of temperature during reproductive phase on yield

Optimum temperature limits to produce 1-2 t/ha yield of gobhi sarson varieties during different phenophases were identified from seven years of experimentation (2003-04 to 2009-10) under irrigated conditions. Maximum temperature regime in the range of 17.0 to 24.4°C (optimum 19.6°C) and minimum temperature in the range of 5.3 to 12.1°C (7.3°C) during vegetative phase and maximum in the range of 15.8-21.2°C (optimum 18.2°C) and minimum temperature in the range of 5.3-10.8°C (7.8°C) during reproductive phase were identified as optimum temperature limits to realize higher yields (Table 3.6).

Further increase in maximum temperature limits up to 20.3-24.4°C (22.4°C) and minimum temperature 7.3-9.3°C (8.3°C) at vegetative phase, 18.7-18.8°C (18.8°C) maximum temperature at reproductive phase and 28.1-29.3°C (28.7°C) maximum temperature and 14.2-15.0°C (14.6°C) minimum temperature at maturity phase increased the yield to >2 t/ha whereas rise in the minimum temperature above 6.0°C during reproductive phase decreases the yield. These optimum temperature limits were tested during 2010-11 to 2013-14 indicating these optimum values were/are valid for the mid hill condition of Himachal Pradesh.

Higher temperatures in the range of 12.5-29.2, 8.5-24.2, 6.2-20.9 and 8.9-26.6°C during emergence, vegetative, reproductive and maturity phases respectively were found to be optimum for Rajasthan conditions (Chauhan *et. al.*, 2013). The lower temperature during the vegetative phase seems to be the constraint for growth and development and consequently lower productivity. Maximum temperature 20.3-24.4°C and minimum temperature 7.3-9.3°C at vegetative phase seems to be optimum for higher productivity (>2t/ha) in rapeseed-mustard in mid hills of the state.

Similarly, higher optimum temperature values have been reported for other stations in India also (adapted from various reports of AICRPAM) which indicate that rapeseed-mustard has not only capacity to withstand higher temperature but also perform better under these conditions.

Table 3.6 Optimum temperature for different phenophases in gobhi sarson at Palampur

Temperatures	Vegetative phases	Reproductive phase	Maturity phase
Yield (>2 t/ha)			
Maximum (°C)	20.3-24.4 (22.4)	18.7-18.8 (18.8)	28.1-29.3 (28.7)
Minimum (°C)	7.3-9.3 (8.3)	6.0-6.1 (6.0)	14.2-15.0 (14.6)
Yield (1– 2 t/ha)			
Maximum (°C)	17.0-24.4* (19.6)	15.8-21.2 (18.2)	22.0-29.7 (25.5)
Minimum (°C)	5.3-12.1 (7.3)	5.3-10.8 (7.8)	8.9-16.6 (13.5)
Yield (<1 t/ha)			
Maximum (°C)	18.9-20.9 (19.9)	15.0-20.9 (19.3)	22.8-24.8 (23.6)
Minimum (°C)	7.0-8.1 (7.4)	4.8-8.8 (7.6)	10.9-12.5 (11.6)

*Threshold temperature limits

3.6 Pheno-thermal Index

Pheno-thermal Index (ratio between accumulated GDD and the number of days during a particular phase) during different phases of crop growth were worked out for five years (2010-11 to 2014-15). Results of the pooled data for all growing environments or dates and varieties are presented in Table 3.7. Pheno-thermal Index (PTI) values ranged from 5.9 to 14.8 degree days/day. The two salient features were (i) within a phase the index showed little variation (ii) among the phases, the highest value was recorded during 90% siliquae filling to physiological maturity followed by 50% flowering to 90% siliquae filling and emergence to first flower. Taking the entire crop period into consideration, the average PTI was found to be nearly constant around a value of 9 degree days/day which was lower than 14.3 degree days/day reported under Delhi conditions (Prasad, 1989).

Table 3.7 Pheno-thermal index during different phenophases in different varieties of gobhi sarson at Palampur

Phenophases/varieties/index	Pheno-thermal Index (growing degree days/day)				
	HPN-1	HPN-3	Hyola-401	GSL-1	ONK-1
Emergence-1 st flower	7.4	7.4	7.5	7.7	7.3
1 st Flower-50% flowering	6.5	6.7	6.7	6.1	5.9
50% Flowering-90% siliquae filling	10.1	9.8	9.5	9.9	10.2
90% Siliquae filling –physiological maturity	14.6	14.8	14.5	13.4	13.8
Entire crop period	8.9	9.0	8.9	8.5	8.4

3.7 El Niño effect on winter rain

In a case study for Himachal Pradesh, El Niño- Its impact on rainfall and productivity of cereals and oilseeds including rapeseed-mustard were evaluated (Prasad *et. al.*, 2014). It was observed that average rainfall during winter season (October-May) during El Niño years was higher than non-El Niño years in 9 out of 10 selected districts of the state. The departure was more than 40 per cent in Kullu and Kangra and more than 20 per cent in Una, Sirmaur, Shimla and Bilaspur districts (Table 3.8). The increase in rainfall was noticed in Hamirpur, Solan and Chamba districts.

Subsequent winter season received higher rainfall. Hence, El Niño has a compensatory effect on winter rains.

Table 3.8 Percent change and anomalies (%) in winter rainfall during El Niño years compared to non-El Niño years' in selected districts of Himachal Pradesh (1971-2009)

District	El Niño years	Non-El Niño years	*PC	El Niño Category		
				Weak	Weak	Weak
Bilaspur	360.8	286.4	26.0	6.4	2.7	60.4
Chamba	603.7	569.5	6.0	-14.9	4.8	23.7
Hamirpur	324.4	280.0	15.9	13.0	12.8	20.6
Kangra	248.3	174.4	42.4	61.6	24.8	41.1
Kullu	336.0	232.8	44.3	60.6	21.4	49.6
Sirmaur	179.5	138.4	29.7	50.3	22.9	18.7
Solan	227.5	199.4	14.1	10.3	3.5	25.6
Shimla	237.7	185.2	28.4	48.7	18.4	20.1
Una	255.7	185.0	38.2	28.7	30.2	52.3
Mandi	371.8	378.9	-1.9	-34.2	11.8	13.1

*PC= per cent change

3.8 Effect of El Niño on area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard

The average area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard during the El Niño years compared to non- El Niño years is given in Table 3.9.

It was observed from the data that akin to rainfall, the area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard during El Niño years was also positively influenced to an extent of 3.7, 13.8 and 8.0%, respectively.

Table 3.9 Per cent change in average area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard during El Niño years compared to Non- El Niño years

Area ('000 ha)			Production ('000 tonnes)			Productivity (kg/ha)		
El Niño	Non- El Niño	*PC	El Niño	Non- El Niño	PC	El Niño	Non- El Niño	PC
8.5	8.2	3.7	3.3	2.9	13.8	372	344.4	8.0

*PC=per cent change

The change in productivity of rapeseed-mustard during different El Niño years is presented in Table 3.10. It could be noticed that the weak El Niño and all categories of El Niño combined increased the rapeseed-mustard productivity in the state.

Table 3.10 Anomalies (%) in productivity of rapeseed-mustard in different categories of El Niño years compared to non El Niño years

El Niño category			
Weak	Moderate	Strong	Combined
42.1	-2.7	-0.4	8.0

3.9 Yield-rainfall relations

The correlation coefficients between rainfall received during different durations in the season and yield in rapeseed-mustard were worked out and presented in Table 3.11. The correlation values obtained were found to be non-significant indicating that the impact of rainfall on yield during these durations was negligible.

Table 3.11 Correlation coefficients between rainfall of different durations and rapeseed-mustard yield in Himachal Pradesh

Monthly/seasonal rainfall during the period	Correlation Coefficient
September	0.188
September to October	0.095
September to November	0.072
September to December	0.028
September to January	0.112
September to February	0.165
September to March	0.142
September to April	0.147
October	-0.253
October to November	-0.270
October to December	-0.251
October to January	-0.062
October to February	0.045
October to March	0.018
October to April	0.024
November	-0.099
November to December	-0.090
November to January	-0.078
November to February	-0.194
November to March	-0.111
November to April	-0.146
December	-0.107
December to January	0.135
December to Feb	0.199
December to March	0.123
December to April	0.125
January	0.239
January to February	0.282
January to March	0.172
January to April	0.177
February	0.145
February to March	0.066
February to April	0.073
March	-0.032
March to April	-0.016
April	0.024

3.10 Impact of rainfall on area, production and productivity

The inter-relations between changes in area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard vis-à-vis rainfall during past forty years (1968-69 to 2007-08) were investigated. It was found that this crop occupied 1st position in terms of area (7.4 thousand hectares), production (2.6 thousand tonnes) and productivity (342 kg/ha). Perusal of the individual

year's data revealed that the maximum area (9.7 thousand hectares) and production (4.9 thousand tonnes) were recorded during the year 1999-2000 (Prasad and Kumari, 2015).

Year-wise trend analysis indicated a significant increase in area, production and productivity. However, pentad-wise trends were significant in case of area only (Table 3.12).

Table 3.12 Trend analysis in area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard

Variable	Mann-Kendall's statistic (S)	Kendall's Tau	Var. (S)	p value Two-tailed test	Interpretation
Year-wise					
Area (000'ha)	573.0	0.705	7908.3	<0.0001	Increasing trend
Prod. (000'tonnes)	361.0	0.444	7913.0	<0.0001	Increasing trend
Productivity (kg/ha)	178.0	0.217	7924.7	0.047	Increasing trend
Pentad-wise					
Area (000'ha)	26.00	0.929	0.000	0.000	Increasing trend
Prod. (000'tonnes)	14.00	0.500	0.000	0.109	No trend
Productivity (kg/ha)	10.00	0.357	0.000	0.275	No trend

A gradual increase in area from 5.3 thousand hectares during 1st pentad (1968-69 to 1972-73) to 9.1 thousand hectares during last pentad (2003-04 to 2007-08) was also noticed (Fig. 3.3). Pentad-wise gradual decrease in production from 1st (1.8 thousand tonnes) to 4th pentad (1.2 thousand tonnes) followed by rapid increase thereafter up to 7th pentad (4.5 thousand tonnes) was observed and as a result, no trend in production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard was indicated by Mann-Kendall's trend test.

Fig 3.3 Pentad-wise rainfall, area, production and productivity in rapeseed-mustard

Pentad-wise per cent shift indicated that the area under rapeseed-mustard showed an increase of 71.7 per cent during 8th pentad over 1st pentad (Table 3.13). Area under rapeseed-mustard has not decreased over its long-term average in none of the pentads. However, in four out of the eight pentads, production and productivity were observed to be less than normal, probably due to aberrant weather conditions.

Table 3.13 Pentad-wise change (%) in area, production, productivity of rapeseed-mustard and rainfall in Himachal Pradesh

Change during	Area (000'ha)	Production (000'tonnes)	Productivity (kg/ha)	Rainfall (mm)
2 nd pentad over 1 st pentad	0.0	-5.6	-3.2	0.41
3 rd pentad over 2 nd pentad	22.6	-5.9	-22.3	67.2
4 th pentad over 3 rd pentad	7.7	-25.0	-34.9	-31.6
5 th pentad over 4 th pentad	17.1	133.3	103.6	17.2
6 th pentad over 5 th pentad	7.3	28.6	21.0	2.4
7 th pentad over 6 th pentad	3.4	25.0	19.6	-18.4
8 th pentad over 7 th pentad	0.0	-17.8	-16.6	71.2
8 th pentad over 1 st pentad	71.7	105.6	20.4	92.6

Since majority of the *rabi* crops are raised under rain fed conditions, the increase in area might be due to 92.6% increase in rainfall and technological interventions including improved varieties during the corresponding period which resulted in 105.6% increase in production and 20.4% increase in productivity. The percent shift in area also showed a significant positive correlation with quantum of *rabi* rainfall ($r=0.86$) which indicated that nearly 74% variation in area sown was due to rainfall variations.

3.11 Contribution of seasonal rainfall towards yield in different mustard varieties

Earlier studies presented in Table 3.14 on comparative performance of Ethiopian mustard (karan rai, variety JTC-1) an important member of rapeseed-mustard group indicated that though, the total seasonal rainfall contributed towards the seed yield; yet, about 30% or more rainfall if received during flowering to siliquae filling phase, might increase the seed yield to a larger extent (Prasad and Kumari, 2006).

Table 3.14 Contribution of seasonal rainfall during flowering and siliquae filling phases and yield performance at Kangra and Dhaulakuan during four seasons

Season	Seasonal Rainfall (mm)	Percent seasonal rainfall during flowering and siliquae filling	Seed yield (kg ha ⁻¹)		Maturity days		Percent increase over Varuna	CD (5%)
			JTC-1	Varuna	JTC-1	Varuna		
Kangra*								
1999-00	641.2	45.5	1276	799	166	148	60	97.6
2000-01	267.0	11.6	1131	425	178	148	166	142.1
2002-03	544.0	38.8	1383	601	175	153	130	120.0
2003-04	406.6	35.6	1560	534	163	143	195	139.0
Mean	464.7	-	1338	590	171	148	127	124.7
C.V. (%)	35	-	14	27	4	3	42	16
Dhaulakuan**								
1999-00	624.1	34.4	1858	900	176	160	106	30.8
2000-01	104.4	10.8	-	742	-	127	-	-
2002-03	160.2	73.8	1265	337	156	137	275	30.0
2003-04	483.4	28.1	647	363	145	139	78	82.0
Mean	343.0	-	1257	586	159	141	115	80.9
C.V. (%)	73	-	48	48	10	10	70	61

* Sowing during last week of October

**Sowing during first week of November

Similar analysis was also undertaken in five varieties viz., GSL-1, HPN-1, HPN-3, Hyola-401 and ONK-1 for six crop seasons (2009-10 to 2014-15) at Palampur. It was found that the different varieties responded differently to the variable amount of rainfall received between flowering to 90% siliquae filling during the season. It was observed that:

- More than 50% (250 mm) of seasonal rainfall (507.9 mm) in early and timely sown GSL-1 produced >1300 kg and in ONK-1 >1100 kg in 5 out of 6 years of study.
- More than 35% (180 mm) of seasonal rainfall (507.9 mm) in early sown HPN-1, HPN-3 and Hyola-401 produced >1400 kg.
- More than 25% (125 mm) of seasonal rainfall (507.9 mm) in late sown GSL-1 and ONK-1 produced >900 kg.
- More than 20% (100 mm) of seasonal rainfall (507.9 mm) in timely sown HPN-1 and HPN-3 produced >1100 kg.
- More than 10% (50 mm) of seasonal rainfall (507.9 mm) in late sown HPN-1, HPN-3 and Hyola-401 produced >500 kg.

Further, the analysis of pooled data indicates that 30% (150 mm) or more rainfall of 500 mm (normal seasonal rainfall) if received during flowering to siliquae filling phase in mid hills, these crops produces higher yields (Table 3.15).

Table 3.15 Contribution of seasonal rainfall received during flowering to siliquae filling and seed yield

Date of sowing/particulars	Per cent contribution	Mean seed yield (kg/ha)
Early sown (October, 20)	35.7-67.1 (51)	1460-1929 (1695)
Timely sown (October, 30)	19.1-57.4 (38)	1300-1579 (1440)
Late sown (November, 30)	8.1-59.0 (34)	1207-1365 (1286)

The variety ONK-1 was found to possess lower yield reduction due to weather extremes i.e., excessively lower and higher temperatures and high rainfall compared to other varieties. Short and sturdy stem makes it lodging tolerant. It produces consistently higher yields (seed and oil) across the locations/climate and resistance/tolerance to pest and diseases thus, possessing wider adaptability (Kumari *et. al.*, 2009).

Yield and weather relations of ONK-1 were worked out for five seasons (2003-04 to 2007-08) at Oilseed Research Station, Kangra and it was found that this variety gave consistently higher yield compared to other varieties even with higher range of mean seasonal temperature varying from 17.4-18.5°C and rainfall of 300.0-644.0 mm during all the seasons studied (Fig 3.4).

Fig 3.4 Performance of ONK-1 compared to other varieties during different crop seasons at Kangra

3.12 Yield-weather relations in gobhi sarson

3.12.1 During vegetative and reproductive phases

Since the correlation coefficients between yield and monthly and seasonal rainfall for Himachal Pradesh as a whole were found to be non-significant hence, it was decided to undertake correlation of weather parameters during vegetative and reproductive phases with yield and yield attributes at Palampur.

The analysis of pooled data indicated that during vegetative phase, several weather parameters viz., morning soil temperature at 10 cm depth, evening soil temperature at 20 cm depth, morning and evening relative humidity and mean relative humidity were found to be significantly correlated with 1000-seed weight, number of primary and secondary branches, plant height, number of siliquae per plant and seed yield (Table 3.16).

During reproductive phase, the morning, evening soil temperature at 5 and 10 cm depths and minimum temperature were found to be significantly correlated with 1000-seed weight, number of primary and secondary branches, plant height, number of siliquae/plant and seed yield. Out of these parameters, soil temperature at 10 cm depth in the morning was found to be significantly and positively related with plant height and number of siliquae per plant.

The analysis indicated that ambient and soil temperature during reproductive phase showed negative influence on the number of primary and secondary branches while they had positive influence on the plant height and number of siliquae per plant.

Table 3.16 Correlation coefficients between weather parameters and yield attributes

Weather parameters	1000- seed weight (g)	Number of primary & secondary branches	Plant height (cm)	Number of siliquae /plant	Seed yield (kg/ha)
Vegetative phase					
Tmax (°C)	-0.47	-0.10	0.30	0.42	0.36
Tmin (°C)	-0.51	-0.35	0.35	0.45	0.16
Soil temp.5cm (M)	-0.39	-0.21	0.25	0.31	0.05
Soil temp.10cm (M)	-0.88**	-0.28	0.55	0.78**	0.39
Soil temp.20cm (M)	0.05	-0.19	-0.01	-0.05	-0.06
Soil temp.5cm (E)	-0.42	-0.24	0.26	0.34	0.15
Soil temp.10cm (E)	-0.10	-0.24	0.08	0.09	0.02
Soil temp.20cm (E)	-0.68**	-0.15	0.44	0.61*	0.49
RH% (M)	0.87**	0.19	-0.55	-0.82**	-0.59*
RH% (E)	0.29	-0.41	-0.11	-0.17	-0.67**
RH% (mean)	0.70**	-0.15	-0.38	-0.70**	-0.70**
BSS (per day)	-0.35	-0.07	0.27	0.41	0.45
Rainfall (mm)	0.45	-0.31	-0.21	-0.31	-0.60
Reproductive phase					
Tmax (°C)	-0.21	-0.54	0.21	0.19	-0.35
Tmin (°C)	-0.05	-0.59*	0.15	0.08	-0.39
Soil temp.5cm (M)	0.13	-0.46	0.00	-0.09	-0.55
Soil temp.10cm (M)	-0.89**	-0.45	0.58*	0.85**	0.18
Soil temp.20cm (M)	0.44	-0.41	-0.19	-0.33	-0.57
Soil temp.5cm (E)	0.35	-0.35	-0.17	-0.28	-0.60*
Soil temp.10cm (E)	0.64*	-0.27	-0.35	-0.52	-0.59*
Soil temp.20cm (E)	-0.24	-0.43	0.20	0.19	-0.36
RH% (M)	0.01	0.44	-0.07	-0.03	0.24
RH% (E)	-0.02	0.37	0.02	0.00	0.39
RH% (mean)	0.00	0.43	-0.03	-0.02	0.33
BSS (per day)	-0.46	-0.15	0.25	0.34	-0.13
Rainfall (mm)	0.14	0.01	0.03	-0.05	0.03

* Significant at $P \leq 0.1$

** Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

n -2 =0.1 (0.582)

n-2 =0.05 (0.666)

Impact of weather parameters on growth and development of five varieties and three sowing dates of gobhi sarson in mid hill irrigated conditions of Himachal Pradesh was studied and from the results of the analysis for one year data of *rabi* 2012-13, it was found that temperature, solar radiation and saturation deficit adversely affected the duration of sowing to first flower and first flower to maturity phases (Kulshreshtha, 2014). The pooled data for these two phenophases was used for analysis and results are presented in Fig. 3.5 and 3.6. Temperature, solar radiation and saturation deficit explained 34, 53 and 58 per cent variation in the duration of sowing to first flower. With the increasing levels of temperature, the duration of sowing to first flower has decreased from 93 to 65 days among different varieties under different sowing dates.

Temperature, solar radiation and saturation deficit explained 97, 24 and 96 per cent variation in the duration of first flower to maturity period. With the increasing levels of temperature, the duration of first flower to maturity decreased from 108 to 66 days among different varieties under different sowing dates. Accordingly, the yield of crop also decreased from 2.22 to 1.50 t/ha with shortening of phenophases caused by increased temperatures due to delay in sowing (Table 3.17).

Table 3.17 Effect of sowing dates on duration (days) of different growth phases and yield in different varieties of gobhi sarson

Date of sowing	Varieties	Sowing to first flower	First flower to maturity	Total crop duration	Yield (t/ha)
D1 10-10-2012	HPN-1	76	108	184	2.01
	HPN-3	80	103	183	2.04
	ONK-1	65	107	172	2.34
	Hyola-401	93	72	165	2.44
	GSL-1	88	66	154	2.27
	Mean	80	91	172	2.22
D2 20-10-2012	HPN-1	76	106	182	2.04
	HPN-3	69	104	173	1.71
	ONK-1	70	102	172	2.00
	Hyola-401	90	74	164	2.43
	GSL-1	87	68	155	1.74
	Mean	78	91	169	1.99
D3 30-10-2012	HPN-1	78	104	182	1.57
	HPN-3	69	102	171	1.12
	ONK-1	93	75	168	1.71
	Hyola-401	90	74	164	1.83
	GSL-1	88	66	154	1.75
	Mean	84	84	168	1.60
D4 10-11-2012	HPN-1	74	100	174	1.37
	HPN-3	67	106	173	1.69
	ONK-1	91	75	166	1.79
	Hyola-401	88	67	155	1.34
	GSL-1	83	71	154	1.32
	Mean	80	86	164	1.50

Fig. 3.5 Duration of sowing to first flower phase of gobhi sarson as influenced by different weather parameters

Fig. 3.6 Duration of first flower to maturity phase of gobhi sarson as influenced by different weather parameters

3.13 Natural resource use efficiency

Natural resource use by different gobhi sarson varieties was quantified in terms of Heat Use Efficiency (HUE), Radiation Use Efficiency (RUE) and Water Use Efficiency (WUE) facilitating identification of varieties suitable for the late and advanced sowing environments. This was accomplished through taking up staggered sowings. It can be inferred from the analysis of the pooled data that differential response exists for HUE, RUE and WUE. In all the varieties and sowing dates, WUE was observed to be higher as compared to other two efficiencies (Table 3.18). Barring few exceptions, the efficiency to use these resources generally decreased with delay in sowing. The variety ONK-1 sown on all the dates was found to be more efficient in respect of heat use and water use than the other varieties studied.

Table 3.18 Resource utilization efficiencies of rapeseed varieties sown on different dates at Palampur

Varieties/ date of sowing	D ₁ - 20 th October			D ₂ - 30 th October			D ₃ - 10 th November		
	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha /MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha/ MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)	HUE (kg/ha/ ° days)	RUE (kg/ha/ MJ)	WUE (kg/ha/ mm)
HPN-1	1.1	0.7	4.1	0.9	0.6	3.5	0.8	0.6	3.5
HPN-3	1.2	0.8	4.6	1.0	0.6	3.7	0.9	0.6	3.4
Hyola-401	1.1	0.7	4.1	0.9	0.5	3.3	0.8	0.5	3.0
GSL-1	1.3	0.7	4.7	0.9	0.5	3.5	0.9	0.6	3.7
ONK-1	1.5	0.8	5.3	1.2	0.6	4.1	1.0	0.5	3.5

3.14 Ideal Plant Type

Rapeseed-mustard plant is photosynthetically inefficient. The comparison of radiation utilization efficiency of wheat and rapeseed-mustard indicates that the radiation utilization efficiency is much lower than wheat. Photosynthetic efficiency of irrigated rapeseed-mustard is nearly half that of irrigated wheat and two-third of rain fed wheat, which might be responsible for low yield in this crop. Vigorous efforts by plant breeders are required to develop an ideal plant type in rapeseed-mustard. Bhargava *et. al.*, 1984 described an ideal plant for *Brassica* sp. as: plant height must be 1-1.25 m with 5-6 primary branches emerging at 30-45° angle from main stem. There should be only 40 siliquae on main stem with 20 siliquae in top two branches and 15 siliquae each on lower three branches. There must be 7-10 leaves with deep root system.

CHAPTER 4

Insect-pests of Rapeseed-Mustard

Rapeseed-mustard is one of the important oleiferous crops and constitute the major source of edible oil for human consumption and cake for animals. Every effort is being made to increase the productivity of this crop by adopting improved package of practices such as use of high yielding varieties, optimum use of fertilizers, irrigation and plant protection measures in order to meet the growing demand of oils (Sirivastava *et. al.*, 2007). Several biotic and abiotic factors are known to pose constraint in the productivity of this crop. More than forty three insect species have been found to be associated with different stages of the rapeseed-mustard crop in India, out of which six viz., mustard aphid *Lipaphis erysimi* (Kaltenbach), Mustard sawfly *Athalia lugens proxima* (Klug), painted bug *Bagrada cruciferarum* (Kirkaldy), leaf miner *Chromatomyia horticola* (Goureau), cabbage caterpillar *Pieris brassicae* (Linnaeus) & cabbage flea beetle (*Phyllotreta cruciferae* Goeze) are of major concern (Sachan and Purwar, 2007) Various aspects of mustard aphid are discussed in detail in this chapter.

4.1 Aphids

Aphids are major pest of rapeseed-mustard. Three species are reported in Himachal Pradesh viz., *L. erysimi* (Kaltenbach) which is pale brownish 2 mm tiny insect, *M. persicae* (Sulzer), light green, sometimes pale in colour and *B. brassicae* (Linnaeus) having whitish in colour. Among the three species of aphids, the mustard aphid *L. erysimi* has been reported as the key pest of rapeseed-mustard in different parts of India. At Palampur, Himachal Pradesh, all the species of aphids have been observed to infest gobhi sarson. However, among these, the cabbage aphid, *B. brassicae* was the most dominant followed by *M. persicae* on the crop sown on different sowing dates and the population of *L. erysimi* was observed to be negligible in (Kumar and Singh, 2013). *B. brassicae* (Linnaeus) is not a serious pest of raya and mustard varieties grown in different regions of India, but is a serious pest in gobhi sarson and is known to cause considerable damage to cabbage and cauliflower also. *M. persicae* (Sulzer) is becoming serious in taramira (*Eruca sativa*), whereas *L. erysimi* remains at low level on this crop. The damage is caused by louse-like, pale, greenish nymphs and adults.

They are seen feeding in large numbers often covering the entire surface of flower buds, shoots, siliquae etc. This insect is found most abundantly from December to March. The avoidable yield losses in various *Brassica* cultivars have been estimated as 46% in yellow sarson, 44% in brown sarson, 31% in Indian musatrd, 36% in gobhi sarson and 23% in karan rai.

This pest is believed to migrate to the hills during summer and there is some evidence that in plains also aphid survives on abandoned stray plants of cabbage and cruciferous weeds. Generally, cloudy and cold weather (temperature, 20°C or below) is very favourable for multiplication of this pest. Both the nymphs and adults suck cell-sap from leaves, stems, inflorescence or the developing siliquae. Vitality of the plant is greatly reduced due to very high population of the pest. The leaves acquire ugly appearance, the flowers fail to form siliquae, and the developing siliquae do not produce healthy seeds.

The distribution of aphids on most plants is not uniform. In general, aphids prefer to feed and reproduce faster on young or senescent than on mature leaves. When more than one species of aphid infest a host plant, the distribution of different species may differ greatly. The distribution of aphids changes during flowering as they tend to move towards flowers. Many aphid species have alternate host plants and there is no continuity of habitat on annual crop plants. Exposed edge-plants or taller *brassica* plants usually have a larger aphid population than plants in the centre of a crop field.

Aphid population count on 10 randomly selected and tagged plants from 10 cm top terminal central shoot of each plant is recorded and averaged at 3-5 days interval from first date of incidence.

L. erysimi (Kaltenbach) is though a key pest for rapeseed-mustard but it was not observed in the experiments conducted at Palampur Centre. Hence, the fluctuation in aphid population of *M. persicae* and *B. brassicae* in relation to weather variables was studied under Palampur conditions for five varieties of gobhi sarson viz., HPN-1, HPN-3, Hyola-401, GSL-1 and ONK-1 for five crop seasons i.e., 2010-11 to 2014-15 for three dates of sowing 20th October, 30th October and 10th November. The weather data during flowering was used and the analysis of pooled data revealed that population build up was found to be higher with mean maximum temperature ranging from 18°C to 20°C and mean minimum temperature of 12-14°C (Fig. 4.1). The population build up also started with thermal humidity index of 4.5 to 5.0. The aphid population started increasing after 110 to 115 days after sowing which coincided with flowering phase, population increased up to 120 to 140 days and thereafter it declined.

Fig. 4.1 Mustard aphid population fluctuations in relation to days after sowing (a), maximum temperature (b), mean temperature (c) and thermal humidity ratio (d) at Palampur

4.2 Thermal time and likely pest population intensity

As discussed in previous sections, aphid infestation on *Brassica* species had been one of the factors causing significant reduction in seed yield. Several regression equations relating aphid population with weather parameters, which are time and location specific, were developed since 1970s. In the areas where western disturbances move over the northern regions of India, high (low) rate of accumulation of degree days by the end of first fortnight of January had shown to be indicative of possible low (high) infestation on the crop in the subsequent weeks. Since, temperature is known to regulate the aphid appearance and its population build up, growing degree days were accumulated from 21st January at three locations viz., Delhi, Mohanpur & Palampur for sake of comparison. It was observed that the rate of accumulation of growing degree days affected the appearance and population buildup. This simple thumb rule could provide a lead-time of a minimum of two to three weeks for being ready to plan preventive/control measures (Anonymous, 2001).

A study conducted by Rao *et. al.* (2013) at these three stations indicate that it was found that for warm climate of New Delhi and Mohanpur, the time to initial occurrence and to attain peak population was relatively shorter than cool climate of Palampur (Table 4.1 & Fig. 4.2) . The possible reason for delayed activity of pest was the influence of temperature on pest as well as on flower initiation. Chakravarthy and Gautam 2002, Patel *et. al.*, 2004 and Prasad *et. al.*, 2013 have shown that flowering stage having predominant yellow colour appearance is the most preferred/favoured phenophase for mustard aphid incidence. The study further indicates that the timing of warming was also found to be associated with appearance and multiplication of this pest.

Table 4.1 Days and thermal time required for first appearance and attainment of peak population of mustard aphid

Name of location	Initial occurrence (DAS)	Attainment of peak population (DAS)	AGDD required for initial appearance (° Cd)	AGDD (mean ± SE) required for attainment of peak population
New Delhi	67	95	810	1053± 237
Mohanpur	50	89	839	1382±417
Palampur	101	143	847	1277±337

Fig 4.2 GDD for predicting aphid population intensity at Delhi (a), Mohanpur (b) & Palampur (c)

4.2.1 Weather parameters and aphid population during February

Different weather parameters *viz.*, maximum/minimum temperature range, mean maximum/minimum temperature, mean temperature and rainfall during 1st, 2nd fortnight of February and mean temperature and rainfall for entire February for eight years under Palampur conditions are presented in Table 4.2. No significant aphid population was recorded during 2004, 2005 and 2007.

During 1st fortnight of February mean maximum temperature varied between 12.4 to 21.4°C, mean minimum temperature 3.1 to 10.4°C, mean temperature 7.8 to 15.9°C and total rainfall 1.6 to 106.0 mm. During 2nd fortnight of February, mean maximum temperature varied between 12.8 to 22.7 °C, mean minimum temperature 5.1 to 12.4°C, mean temperature 10.1 to 17.6 °C and total rainfall 3.2 to 110.8 mm. During entire month mean temperature varied between 10.3 to 16.7°C and total rainfall 11.6 to 165.2 mm. This analysis indicated that warmer (higher mean temperature, 10.1 to 17.6°C) and drier during 2nd fortnight of February is highly conducive for incidence and spread of aphid.

Table 4.2 Weather parameters and aphid population during February in different years at Palampur

Parameter	2003	2006	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Weather Parameters (First fortnight)								
Maximum temp (°C)	11.0-18.5	20.0-23.0	5.7-18.0	12.5-21.5	11.5-20.0	12.0-23.0	9.0-18.0	10.2-20.2
Minimum temp (°C)	4.0-7.5	9.0-11.5	0.4-8.7	5.5-9.5	2.0-10.5	4.5-12.5	0.0-8.0	1.4-9.0
Mean max temp (°C)	16.6	21.4	12.4	18.0	16.2	18.8	14.6	17.0
Mean min temp (°C)	5.8	10.4	3.1	7.0	5.0	8.2	4.2	5.7
Mean temp (°C)	11.2	15.9	7.8	12.2	10.6	13.5	9.4	11.3
Total rainfall (mm)	23.8	1.6	80.8	28.8	106.0	30.6	65.9	86.6
Aphid appearance in February	during 2 nd week	during 3 rd week	during 3 rd week	during 2 nd week	during 3 rd week	during 4 th week	during 3 rd week	during 3 rd week
Weather Parameters (Second fortnight)								
Maximum temp (°C)	12.5-21.5	19.0-25.0	5.7-18.0	18.0-21.5	17.5-23.5	8.0-19.0	12.5-20.5	9.2-20.5
Minimum temp (°C)	2.01-1.5	9.0-15.1	0.4-8.7	5.0-9.5	4.5-12.0	3.0-7.5	3.2-17.4	3.5-11.0
Mean max temp. (°C)	17.7	22.7	18.7	19.9	20.0	15.0	17.4	12.8
Mean min temp (°C)	6.5	12.4	7.8	7.2	7.3	5.1	7.5	6.8
Mean temp (°C)	12.1	17.6	13.3	13.6	13.6	10.1	12.5	11.3
Total rainfall (mm)	54.4	10.0	17.7	3.2	14.6	110.8	14.0	78.6
Weather Parameters (Entire February)								
Mean temp (°C)	11.6	16.7	10.3	13.1	12.1	11.8	11.0	11.3
Total rainfall (mm)	78.2	11.6	17.7	32.0	120.6	141.4	79.9	165.2

Parameters associated:

Phenological stage: Flowering stage

Higher maximum temperature: positive effect

Lower minimum temperature: negative effect

Higher after noon RH: negative effect

Higher rainfall: negative effect (due to dislodging of pest)

Aphid outbreak: second fortnight of February

Aphid peak population: March end

4.2.2 Aphid populations and their weather relations in gobhi sarson at Palampur

In order to assess the aphid incidence, build up and their weather relations in three gobhi sarson varieties (HPN-1, HPN-3 and Hyola-401), two field experiments were conducted at Palampur during *rabi* seasons (2010-11 and 2011-12). The crop was sown on three dates representing three thermal environments *i.e.*, October 25, November 2 and November 10 in each season under unprotected conditions. Recommended package of practices were followed to raise the crop. For aphid population count in each treatment, 10 plants were randomly selected, tagged and aphids were counted from 10 cm top terminal central shoot of each plant at 3-5 days interval from first date of incidence (Singh and Lal, 1999). Seven observations starting from February 21, 23, 27, March 2, 7, 11 and 15 during 2010-11 and thirteen observations from February 21, 25, 29, March 3, 7, 12, 16, 20, 25, 30, April 5, 10 and 16 during 2011-12 were recorded and average population per plant was calculated.

Accordingly, dates of incidence, economic threshold level, ETL (30 aphids/plant) and peak population were calculated. Daily weather data on maximum and minimum temperatures (Tmax and Tmin), morning and evening relative humidity (RH I and RH II) and rainfall records of agrometeorological observatory of the university three days prior to incidence, ETL and peak population observed were used for the study. Seed yields (kg/ha) from each treatment were recorded at harvest and analysed statistically (Panse and Sukhatme, 1985).

During 2010-11, aphids appeared on 21st February in all the dates of sowing, however, the population was higher in crop sown on third date. First ETL in crop occurred on 23rd February whereas peak activity of *B. brassicae* (mean of three dates, 269.3/10 cm terminal shoot/plant) and *M. persicae* (93/10 cm terminal shoot/plant) was noticed on 2nd

March (Table 4.3). ETL was found to be associated with Tmax of 18.0°C (17.0-19.0), Tmin 6.2°C (5.5-7.5), Tmean 11.6°C (10.8-12.8), RH I 72% (69- 74), RH II 65 (47-93) and RH mean 68% (60-81). Peak incidence of aphid was associated with Tmax of 15.7°C (14.5-17.5), Tmin 6.0°C (4.0-8.0), Tmean 10.2°C (7.5 -12.8), RH I 76% (65-85), RH II 72% (51-86) and RH mean 74% (52-84). Though, the Tmean was higher by 3°C compared to 2011-12 but 38.5 mm of rain occurred during 6- 12th March might have caused dislodging of the pests.

Incidentally, aphid incidence during 2011-12 was also noticed on 21st February, 2012 and on the same day, the population was found to be above ETL. Incidence of aphid and ETL were associated with Tmax of 17.2°C (16.5-18.5), Tmin 7.2°C (6.5 - 8.0), Tmean 12.2°C (11.8-12.8), RH I 85% and RH II 56%.

Table 4.3 Weather parameters three days prior to incidence, ETL and peak population of aphids in gobhi sarson during 2010-11 and 2011-12

Weather parameter	At incidence	At ETL	At peak population
Rabi, 2010-11			
Mean max. temperature (°C)	16.4	18.0	15.7
Mean min. temperature (°C)	5.2	6.2	6.0
Mean temperature (°C)	10.8	11.6	10.2
RH I	77	72	76
RH II	55	65	72
Mean RH	66	68	74
Total rainfall (mm)	0.0	1.0	1.8
Aphid population:			
<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i>			
25 th October	15	62	233
2 nd November	21	79	272
10 th November	36	85	303
<i>Myzus persicae</i>			
25 th October	9	23	70
2 nd November	12	27	85
10 th November	19	31	124
Rabi, 2011-12			
Mean max. temperature (°C)	17.2	17.2	19.6
Mean min. temperature (°C)	7.2	7.2	7.0
Mean temperature (°C)	12.2	12.2	13.3
RH I	85	85	57
RH II	56	56	36
Mean RH	71	71	47
Total rainfall (mm)	9.6	9.6	0.0
Aphid population:			
<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i>			
25 th October	106	106	869
2 nd November	145	145	1204
10 th November	201	201	1351
<i>Myzus persicae</i>			
25 th October	56	56	412
2 nd November	78	78	821
10 th November	86	86	940

4.3 Conceptual model for forewarning mustard aphid

Based on the observation made a conceptual model was proposed (Fig. 4.3). Under mid-hill condition of Himachal Pradesh the rapeseed-mustard crop when sown during early, timely and late sown conditions, the 50% flowering stage will commence on 2nd, 3rd and 4th week of February. The early sowing date experiences temperature $>21^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is not favourable for aphid attack. It was observed that the aphid population build up starts from 2nd week of February and was maximum after 3rd week of February. This shows that the early sown crop escapes the aphid attack while the late sown crop is highly infested with the aphids due to congenial weather conditions (maximum temperature is $13-16^{\circ}\text{C}$, mean temperature $3-4^{\circ}\text{C}$, RH 47-66% and rainfall up to 5 mm).

Fig. 4.3 Conceptual model for forewarning mustard aphid

4.4 Integrated pest management (IPM)

The knowledge of biology and ecology of an insect pest is essential to find out the weak links in its life history so that these can be utilized in evolving the integrated pest management programme for the targeted pests. Considering the complexity of insect problem of rapeseed-mustard, development of improved production technology and adoption by the farmers is of paramount importance in raising the productivity of rapeseed-mustard crop. Technologically vital and economically viable components of Integrated Pest Management

(IPM) are presented in Fig. 4.4. The role of weather, weather forecast and forewarning models is highlighted.

Fig 4.4 Components of integrated pest management (IPM) in rapeseed-mustard

CHAPTER 5

Agromet advisories and contingency plans

5.1 Agro Advisory Service

Agro Advisory Service Units (AASU) program for dissemination of medium range weather forecast from the National Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecast (NCMRWF) was raised from 83 units during early 1990s at the erstwhile NARP Centres of ICAR located in different agro climatic regions to presently 127 units. AASU at Palampur Centre was established during 1992. Based on the MRWF received twice a week, weather based agro advisories are prepared by these units located at the State Agricultural University Research Centres for dissemination to the farming community through various communication media. Since then this centre is also sending specific advisories once in a week based on forecasted weather event having potential impact on agricultural activities warranting suitable weather based managements. Some of the sample advisories on sowing, irrigation/drainage, applications of agrochemicals and harvesting/threshing windows for rapeseed-mustard crop prepared and issued to the farmers by AICRPAM, Palampur Centre through the National Mobile Governance Initiative, Mobile Seva, Ministry of communication and Information Technology, Government of India (<http://esms.mgov.gov.in>) during past couple of years on rapeseed-mustard are listed in Table 5.1 to 5.4.

Table 5.1 Advisories suggesting sowing windows

Advisory issued on date	Advisories
19.10.2013	काँगड़ा जिला में आगामी चार-पांच दिनों तक मौसम साफ रहने का अनुमान है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि <ul style="list-style-type: none">धान की कटाई व गहाई अति शीघ्र कर लें तथा सरसों व इस समय लगाई जाने वाली गेहूँ की किस्मों की बुआई कर के भूमि के अंदर उपलब्ध नमी का पूरा फायदा उठायें।
31.10.2014	आगामी तीन-चार दिन में प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ बने रहने की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि <ul style="list-style-type: none">सरसों व इस समय लगाई जाने वाली गेहूँ की किस्मों की बुआई कर के भूमि के अंदर उपलब्ध नमी का पूरा फायदा उठायें।

Table 5.2 Advisories suggesting irrigation/ drainage

Advisory issued on date	Advisories
25.02.2014	आगामी चार-पांच दिनों तक काँगड़ा जिला में 65 मि० मी० वर्षा की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • किसान विभिन्न फसलों में सिंचाई न करें।
07.03.2014, 21.03.2014 & 25.03.2014	आगामी चार-पांच दिनों में काँगड़ा जिला में वर्षा की सम्भावना है। अतः सलाह दी जाती है कि <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • किसान विभिन्न फसलों में सिंचाई न करें।

Table 5.3 Advisories suggesting application of fertilizers, insecticides and pesticides

Advisory issued on date	Advisories
24.01.2014	More aphids attack is expected in rapeseed-mustard after rains, for its control spray 30 ml Cypermethrin 10 EC per 30 litre of water per kanal area.
07.03.2014, 21.03.2014, 25.03.2014 & 28.03.2014	Mustard aphid multiplication is expected after rains. Farmers are advised to spray 750 ml Cypermethrin or Metasystox in 750 l water/ ha. These insecticides should be sprayed on the crop during evening hours to avoid harm to honeybees.
03.11.2015	दीमक प्रभावित खेतों में बीज का उपचार क्लोरपाईरीफास 20 ई० सी० 40 मि० ली० को 250 मि० ली० पानी में घोल कर 10 किलो बीज में छिड़के या प्रति कर्नाल 80 मि० ली० क्लोरपाईरीफास 1 किलो रेत में मिलाकर बजाई से पहले खेत में मिलाएँ।
26.02.2016	सरसों वर्ग की तिलहनी फसलों में तेले का प्रकोप हो सकता है। अधिक प्रकोप होने पर फसल में 30मि ली साईपरमैथ्रीन 10) ई० सी० (या मिथाईल डेमिटान 25) ई० सी० (या डाईमिथोएट 30) ई० सी० (30 कोलीटर पानी में मिला कर प्रति कनाल छिड़काव करें।

Table 5.4 Advisories suggesting harvesting and threshing windows

Advisory issued on date	Advisories
11.04.2014	आगामी दो-तीन दिनों में प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में बारिश की संभावना है अतः किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि पक्की हुई सरसों की कटाई पूरी कर लें।
19.04.2014	आगामी दो दिनों में प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में बारिश की संभावना है अतः किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि अभी फसल की कटाई न करें तथा कटी हुई सरसों का सुरक्षित भंडारण कर लें।
27.03.2015	आगामी एक-दो दिनों के बाद प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में हल्की से मध्यम बारिश के साथ तापमान में कमी आने तथा छिटपुट स्थानों पर ओलावृष्टि की सम्भावना भी है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि पक कर तैयार हो चुकी सरसों की अतिशीघ्र कटाई कर लें।
15.03.2016	आगामी दो दिन तक प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में मौसम साफ़ रहने तथा तापमान में 3-4 डि० सै० तक वृद्धि होने की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है कि पक कर तैयार हुई सरसों की कटाई अतिशीघ्र कर लें।
30.03.2016	प्रदेश के लगभग सभी जिलों में आगामी एक-दो दिनों के बाद हल्की बारिश होने तथा तापमान में और

	वृद्धि होने की सम्भावना है। किसानों को सलाह दी जाती है की पक कर तैयार हो चुकी सरसों की अतिशीघ्र कटाई कर लें।
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5.2 Contingency plans

Need for contingency planning is increasingly being realized as an important component of preparedness to minimize the adverse impact of weather aberrations on agriculture and allied sectors in the context of increasing climatic variability. Prior to any systematic centralised procedure at CSKHPKV Palampur, sporadic local efforts were being made to prepare contingency plans. An example for one of six scenarios in which early onset of winter rains for early sowing of gobhi sarson and wheat were proposed is presented in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5 Contingency plan for early onset of winter rains in mid-hills of Himachal Pradesh

Scenario	Chances of occurrence (% of years)	Contingency Plan
Onset before 15 October	10	Toria + Gobhi sarson or gobhi sarson (var. HPN-1) and Wheat variety VL-616 may be raised.

State-wise technical documents comprising of suggested contingency measures related to crops were urgently required in the country. Realising the importance of increasing losses in different sectors of agriculture vis-à-vis rising extreme weather events, the Department of Agriculture and Cooperation, Ministry of Agriculture, Government of India, sponsored a country-wide effort under the aegis of ICAR. A standard template for preparation of district level contingency plans was formulated by CRIDA, Hyderabad and shared with all the SAUs. Several workshops were organized at CRIDA, Hyderabad, CSWCRTI, Dehradun and finally at CSK HPKV, Palampur to finalize the district level plans for Himachal Pradesh which were later published (Prasad *et. al.*, 2013).

Suggested contingency measures for management of rapeseed-mustard crop during delay in the onset of winter rains, heat wave, cold wave, frost, hailstorm, high velocity winds, unseasonal rains etc., during different phases of crop for both rain fed and irrigated condition are presented Table 5.6 and 5.7.

Table 5.6 Plans for delay in onset of winter rains by 2, 4 and 6 weeks

Rainfall abnormality	Suggested contingency measures		Agronomic measures
	Normal cropping system	New cropping system	
Delay in winter showers By 2 weeks (First week of Jan.), By 4 weeks (3 rd week of Jan.) By 6 weeks (2 nd week of Feb.)	Maize –Toria - Wheat Maize+ Pulses- Wheat +Sarson	In Zone I & II <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intercropping of wheat with rapeseed/mustard/peas • Gobhi sarson 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase seed rate by 25% • Reduce the nitrogen fertilizer dose by 25% • Close spacing • Addition of organic manures (FYM/compost) to the soil at least 5-10t/ha. • Adopt soil moisture conservation measures with locally available mulch.

Table 5.7 Plans for management of extreme events

Extreme event type	Suggested contingency measures			
	Seedling / nursery stage	Vegetative stage	Reproductive stage	At harvest
Heat wave/cold wave/frost	Apply light and frequent irrigation wherever irrigation facilities are available			
Hailstorm/high velocity wind/ unseasonal rains	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At harvest stage, harvest the crop according to weather condition and weather forecast. • Stake the produce in the safe or sheltered places in the event of unseasonal hailstorm/storm/high velocity wind/unseasonal rain 			

Implementation of contingency plans are still at infancy in India and it requires elaborated arrangements for their effective implementation.

CHAPTER 6

Summary

Agro-meteorological information in respect of rapeseed-mustard crop reported in several books, reports, bulletins, research papers, varietal released proposals, related documents and work done under All India Coordinated Research Project on Agrometeorology, Palampur Centre was compiled in this bulletin. Some of the key points emanated are presented here under:

- Rapeseed (gobhi sarson) completes its emergence in 10 days with mean temperature 19.8°C and 127 growing degree days. For completion of 50% flowering and physiological maturity, the crop requires 852 and 1530 growing degree days, respectively. Duration from sowing to first flower was lowest in case of early sowing (20th October) and highest in normal sowing (30th October). However, GDD for sowing to occurrence of different phenological stages was highest in early sowing only. The reduction in duration under delayed sowing was more pronounced in post flowering stages.
- Increase in temperature, solar radiation and saturation deficit in delayed sowing decreased phasic/total duration of the crop and thereby decreased the rapeseed-mustard yield from 2.44 to 1.12 t/ha.
- For obtaining >2 t/ha yield under mid-hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh rapeseed-mustard during vegetative phase requires optimum temperature of 20.3-24.4°C maximum, 7.3-9.3°C minimum and 14.4°C mean. The ambient and soil temperature during reproductive phase showed negative influence on the number of primary and secondary branches while they had positive influence on the plant height and number of siliquae per plant.
- Higher positive or lower negative deviations over the season produced correspondingly higher yields in three out of five seasons studied.
- The average rainfall during winter season (October-May) following the El Niño was higher than non-El Niño years in the state. The positive departure was more than 40 per cent in Kullu and Kangra and more than 20 per cent in Una, Sirmaur, Shimla and

Bilaspur districts. Consequently average area, production and productivity of rapeseed-mustard increased by 3.7, 13.8 and 8.0%, respectively.

- The PTI was found to be nearly constant around a value of 9 degree days/day which was lower than 14.3 degree days/day under plains. Irrigated rapeseed-mustard is nearly photosynthetically half efficient as irrigated wheat and two-third as rain fed wheat which might be responsible for low yield of the crop.
- Growing degree days for attaining peak population were the same (840 units) for Delhi, Mohanpur and Palampur but time to initial occurrence and peak population of mustard aphid was relatively longer for cool climate of Palampur by 43 and 50 days, respectively than warm climate of Delhi and Mohanpur. Incidence of aphid and economic threshold level were associated with maximum temperature of 17.2°C, minimum 7.2°C, mean 12.2°C, RH I 85% and RH II 56% under mid-hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh. Warmer (10.1 to 17.6°C) and drier 2nd fortnight of February is highly favourable for incidence and spread of aphids. Therefore, early sowing is not only beneficial for obtaining higher seed yields but also for escaping the aphids attack under mid hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh.

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Normal weekly temperature (°C) in different rapeseed-mustard growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Week	Akrot		Bajaura		Berthin		Dhaulakuan		Kangra		Malan		Palampur		Salooni		Shimla	
	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min
40	32.2	20.1	29.2	12.6	30.9	18.5	30.9	17.4	30.5	19.6	28.5	17.2	26.0	15.3	26.5	14.4	22.7	13.1
41	31.3	17.4	28.5	10.2	29.9	15.3	30.6	14.9	29.5	17.1	27.9	15.9	25.5	14.3	26.1	14.4	21.9	12.3
42	30.7	15.3	26.8	8.0	29.2	13.3	29.7	12.7	28.6	15.1	27.2	14.5	24.6	13.1	25.5	13.5	20.8	10.9
43	29.9	14.3	25.9	6.6	27.9	11.1	28.4	11.1	27.5	12.9	26.1	13.2	23.7	12.2	24.1	12.6	20.1	10.3
44	29.2	13.2	26.0	5.8	27.1	9.7	27.9	10.2	27.1	12.2	26.0	12.6	23.2	11.6	24.5	12.6	19.4	9.8
45	28.1	12.1	24.4	4.7	26.5	8.7	27.0	9.3	26.1	11.3	25.5	11.8	22.0	10.6	24.1	12.5	18.6	9.0
46	26.8	10.7	23.7	3.4	25.9	7.1	26.1	8.1	24.6	10.4	23.8	10.7	21.2	9.5	23.6	11.8	18.0	8.6
47	25.8	9.6	22.0	2.5	24.3	6.1	25.0	7.1	23.7	9.0	22.8	10.0	20.4	8.5	22.7	11.4	17.0	7.6
48	24.3	8.5	20.9	1.3	23.5	5.1	23.9	5.7	23.0	7.3	21.9	8.7	19.0	7.4	22.2	11.1	16.3	6.7
49	24.1	7.9	20.1	1.0	22.8	4.5	23.4	4.9	22.5	7.4	21.4	8.0	19.1	7.4	21.2	11.2	16.2	7.1
50	22.3	8.0	18.0	1.0	20.5	4.6	22.0	5.0	20.8	7.1	19.8	7.7	17.7	6.7	20.3	10.3	14.3	5.5
51	21.9	6.8	17.5	0.6	20.7	4.0	21.5	4.3	20.7	6.0	19.3	7.1	17.4	6.2	20.0	9.9	14.4	5.6
52	20.3	5.4	16.6	0.3	19.3	3.1	20.2	3.7	19.4	4.5	18.7	6.2	16.0	5.1	18.7	9.2	13.1	4.3
1	18.1	5.3	15.5	0.6	17.9	3.4	18.9	4.5	18.1	4.7	17.1	5.3	15.2	4.7	18.4	8.3	12.1	3.6
2	19.6	6.0	15.8	0.8	18.9	3.0	18.9	4.1	18.6	4.8	16.7	5.5	15.2	4.9	18.5	8.6	11.7	3.4
3	18.6	6.8	15.1	1.2	18.1	4.7	19.0	4.6	18.0	5.8	16.5	5.8	14.8	4.8	17.6	7.9	11.6	3.3
4	19.9	5.9	16.7	1.2	19.0	3.2	20.4	4.2	18.5	5.1	16.9	5.7	15.1	5.0	18.0	8.0	12.6	3.7
5	20.8	7.2	17.3	2.0	20.4	4.1	21.3	5.0	19.3	6.6	18.1	6.5	15.8	5.6	16.8	7.2	13.2	4.4
6	20.6	8.7	17.0	3.0	20.2	6.5	21.6	6.1	19.2	7.4	17.7	6.6	15.9	5.9	15.7	6.3	12.9	4.2
7	21.8	9.1	16.7	3.5	20.1	6.2	22.1	6.7	19.6	8.1	18.1	7.0	16.5	6.5	15.9	6.7	12.7	4.0
8	23.4	9.9	18.3	4.0	22.9	7.3	23.2	7.1	21.3	9.3	20.2	7.8	17.4	6.7	17.0	7.4	13.6	4.6
9	24.6	10.3	19.3	4.6	24.1	7.9	24.1	7.8	22.6	8.7	20.9	8.6	18.3	8.1	18.1	8.1	15.0	6.0
10	26.3	10.9	21.4	5.3	25.8	8.0	26.3	8.6	23.9	10.0	22.3	9.1	19.8	9.2	19.0	8.1	16.5	7.0
11	28.2	12.7	21.7	5.9	26.8	9.3	27.3	10.0	25.3	10.4	23.2	9.9	20.6	9.9	19.7	8.3	17.2	7.8
12	29.3	14.2	22.4	6.6	28.7	10.5	29.0	11.3	27.3	11.6	25.3	11.0	21.7	10.6	19.0	7.7	17.8	8.5
13	30.6	15.0	23.5	7.2	28.2	11.0	29.7	11.4	27.9	12.5	25.9	11.2	22.9	11.8	19.6	8.1	18.9	9.5
14	32.4	15.9	24.7	7.9	30.0	11.4	31.9	12.3	29.2	13.9	26.7	12.4	24.2	12.7	20.0	8.2	20.1	10.5
15	34.4	17.5	26.1	8.7	31.9	12.2	33.1	13.2	30.6	13.9	27.8	13.1	25.5	13.9	20.0	8.2	21.0	11.6
16	34.7	18.5	27.1	9.3	32.5	13.9	34.3	14.8	31.0	15.2	29.1	13.4	26.6	15.0	19.8	7.9	22.2	12.6
17	36.4	19.5	27.8	10.3	33.2	14.1	35.8	15.6	32.8	16.7	30.7	14.9	27.9	16.5	20.4	8.7	23.3	13.5
18	37.0	21.1	28.7	11.4	34.2	15.9	36.2	17.2	33.1	17.9	31.9	16.2	28.9	17.2	20.6	8.8	24.0	14.4

Normal weekly rainfall in different rapeseed-mustard growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Station	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	
Akrot	9.9	7.0	2.7	5.0	2.1	0.5	2.1	0.3	0.7	1.4	5.7	4.9	3.5	5.9	6	11.4	12.6	8.4	14.5	13.9	10.6	8.7	4.2	13.2	3.7	5.3	2.2	2.6	9.5	8.0	3.5	
Arki	5.9	7.9	8.9	2.1	1.2	2.5	2.0	3.0	3.7	1.0	8.2	8.3	9.4	8.2	9.1	13.1	19.8	10.0	16.8	21.3	18.7	13.3	17.0	14.6	14.8	7.9	6.4	7.3	8.1	7.5	8.7	
Bajaura	4.8	4.8	13.3	2.4	0.5	7.0	3.4	3.5	6.5	3.6	7.9	10.5	10.2	10.7	13.9	23.0	11.8	11.5	31.7	31.6	22.4	27.3	22.1	32.0	31.5	16.9	14.0	17.2	18.2	18.2	17.6	
Banjar	4.3	5.4	5.4	4.0	1.6	6.1	2.1	5.0	2.9	2.5	6.9	9.6	9.1	10.5	13.8	24.5	12.6	10.7	26.8	22.4	19.5	29.3	14.8	27.1	20.1	17.5	10.4	14.4	15.5	17.2	14.7	
Berthin	3.6	9.6	2.2	3.6	0.2	2.1	1.5	2.0	1.1	2.4	12.2	3.8	1.2	4.9	8.3	17.9	15.4	7.9	22.9	24.9	5.3	16.3	4.8	20.3	18.6	2.3	4.0	6.2	7.6	3.7	3.8	
Bhoranj	10.5	4.4	1.3	1.0	1.7	1.5	0.8	0.2	0.1	2.1	3.9	2.0	6.8	5.8	9.3	20.5	15.8	10.1	25.3	25.6	4.8	22.6	7.3	10.9	13.9	3.3	10.9	4.6	7.5	2.9	9.2	
Chachiot	3.6	11.4	0.6	0.0	0.7	0.0	1.1	1.4	0.4	2.0	8.2	0.8	0.6	5.3	5.4	19.5	4.4	4.6	21.9	11.1	3.5	9.9	10.7	5.8	7.2	8.2	0.7	4.8	19.5	4.9	10.9	
Dehra	8.7	7.5	3.6	3.3	1.8	1.0	3.4	2.8	3.0	2.9	7.5	6.3	14.6	8.1	9.8	18.7	11.4	10.9	12.4	22.1	20.1	14.2	13.7	15.8	11.7	9.1	6.2	6.5	4.1	9.7	8.2	
Dharamshala	15.3	11.9	8.0	5.7	4.2	2.9	4.5	3.3	6.8	3.7	10.2	11.5	20.5	20.5	16.2	26.6	23.3	19.3	23.7	33.7	25.8	30.5	24.8	27.8	29.5	17.0	14.0	17.2	13.5	12.7	13.3	
Dhaulakuan	7.5	4.9	5.7	1.3	0.5	1.4	0.9	2.5	1.2	3.1	6.0	3.3	15.6	4.8	11.0	13.5	9.4	5.2	22.4	23.0	11.3	16.1	7.5	8.4	7.8	6.8	7.5	3.8	3.7	4.4	16.5	
Ghumarwin	3.6	8.8	9.2	7.4	2.6	5.4	3.3	2.1	1.0	1.3	4.0	8.3	11.9	10.9	9.6	15.0	16.6	18.0	17.1	18.6	18.5	23.6	8.8	16.7	13.8	9.7	4.7	7.2	6.8	11.4	8.8	
Hamirpur	5.4	10.8	7.3	4.9	2.5	1.0	2.6	4.2	2.6	2.2	7.4	6.3	12.9	8.1	14.5	13.0	19.8	15.8	17.9	29.8	16.0	18.8	13.7	16.8	16.5	7.9	7.7	8.4	7.7	10.0	9.7	
Jogindernagar	16.4	11.5	5.0	2.0	1.9	6.3	2.2	0.5	2.0	5.1	17.3	7.0	0.4	13.1	8.6	32.1	19.4	12.8	31.5	28.2	11.2	30.8	12.1	24.4	19.8	10.0	2.6	15.9	39.4	12.4	3.4	
Jubbal	11.4	10.8	5.8	5.7	3.8	1.7	1.1	3.2	2.7	1.8	7.5	14.5	12.1	9.2	14.8	18.7	27.5	14.2	18.1	22.9	20.3	23.5	16.4	16.8	20.9	15.9	9.6	9.9	17.1	15.9	18.4	
Kandaghat	8.7	10.5	4.6	3.2	3.7	2.5	2.0	3.5	3.8	2.4	9.7	8.3	19.5	9.1	10.3	11.8	17.0	11.7	18.9	16.4	25.5	17.4	13.0	13.1	14.6	8.4	7.1	5.5	7.6	8.6	7.8	
Kangra	5.9	9.2	5.1	4.6	1.7	2.9	9.8	2.7	0.6	3.2	8.1	4.0	6.8	3.9	9.5	27.3	10.9	16.0	27.8	16.0	17.6	18.8	4.3	17.3	8.9	7.1	11.4	7.0	14.1	5.8	5.6	
Karsog	4.0	6.2	8.4	3.6	2.2	3.7	3.0	4.7	2.0	1.2	6.6	3.9	10.0	7.6	9.0	19.4	22.2	9.0	19.1	21.0	17.3	23.1	16.3	23.3	18.3	12.9	10.3	13.3	14.9	11.6	12.5	
Kasuli	5.8	5.6	11.4	2.1	3.2	3.2	3.3	1.8	2.7	1.8	6.8	6.9	11.9	9.4	12.2	9.0	11.6	11.7	18.9	25.8	12.7	13.9	12.9	14.3	17.3	13.2	7.4	5.6	7.9	6.8	10.8	
Keylong	3.1	3.8	3.2	2.4	2.3	5.4	4.5	4.1	2.0	4.3	7.3	8.1	16.1	6.3	8.0	14.0	12.5	6.9	18.9	20.5	23.7	22.0	22.4	26.9	31.9	13.2	14.2	15.9	12.0	12.2	10.2	
Kotkhai	2.2	9.6	5.2	1.0	2.2	2.4	1.2	2.0	1.7	3.7	5.1	3.8	8.1	6.1	8.7	11.0	13.9	12.9	15.4	12.8	15.7	14.6	9.8	8.1	11.3	9.7	10.5	8.3	7.0	13.2	13.2	
Kumarsain	3.7	7.8	3.2	2.9	3.1	3.2	3.1	1.8	2.7	2.4	4.5	6.8	9.1	7.1	8.6	15.0	13.6	15.0	18.2	14.2	13.7	15.0	10.1	14.0	17.6	7.8	9.4	10.8	10.5	12.5	12.4	
Malan	12.3	6.9	2.5	4.3	0.3	3.5	8.1	0.6	0.5	1.6	13.5	2.9	4.2	7.4	16.4	24.7	15.4	14.5	28.9	22.0	14.2	22.0	8.3	15.6	15.2	6.5	4.7	4.0	12.4	6.5	4.8	
Mandi	36.5	15.2	10.3	2.6	10.7	35.9	3.8	2.9	8.1	44.3	9.3	9.6	9.6	20.9	28.8	14.8	27.8	23.0	24.8	18.9	17.9	16.4	26.5	13.5	17.2	11.9	26.7	7.9	10.8	12.9	13.7	
Mashobra	6.9	18.3	17.9	8.2	5.4	2.5	4.8	2.7	1.6	1.4	7.3	9.2	12.0	8.0	14.5	22.3	22.8	18.1	28.5	35.9	25.4	27.2	13.5	22.6	23.3	17.8	12.6	10.6	15.2	19.1	17.8	
Nadaun	11.8	4.9	4.7	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.4	1.3	2.5	13.3	3.5	4.2	6.6	4.5	10.1	14.3	5.7	10.0	16.8	18.2	15.9	8.0	2.2	17.1	7.5	8.5	5.5	2.7	6.2	2.5	3.0	
Nahan	6.6	10.3	3.3	1.7	0.9	1.4	0.7	2.7	2.6	1.4	4.0	7.4	17.5	6.9	8.9	12.7	11.6	7.7	20.8	18.1	10.0	11.3	8.2	10.0	9.2	4.7	2.5	6.2	3.5	4.4	7.2	
Nichar	1.9	4.4	6.7	2.8	5.3	2.5	4.8	4.2	2.6	3.1	5.2	7.3	12.2	18.0	27.1	17.1	31.0	29.1	30.8	30.9	28.8	22.0	28.4	22.8	32.6	29.6	21.5	16.4	13.7	19.8	17.8	
Nurpur	21.1	30.9	5.7	5.6	9.1	45.5	6.0	6.0	8.2	39.5	8.3	6.7	21.6	17.7	27.5	15.0	18.2	15.6	44.5	22.5	21.6	15.7	40.0	17.9	16.8	8.7	38.4	19.3	6.5	12.4	10.1	
Pachhad	9.6	10.1	3.1	2.2	2.0	0.7	2.6	2.9	4.1	0.8	5.2	10.6	13.9	5.8	8.7	13.1	14.4	13.1	21.0	24.9	10.7	12.9	14.3	11.6	9.9	8.6	3.8	7.4	15.9	5.3	6.8	
Palampur	11.7	12.6	6.3	3.1	2.8	4.0	4.0	2.7	5.9	3.7	12.2	9.3	18.7	16.4	20.3	20.3	31.0	16.4	26.1	35.5	25.4	27.6	19.0	27.0	31.3	14.5	14.7	13.0	12.7	12.2	15.3	
Paunta	4.7	2.3	10.2	0.1	0.3	1.3	1.6	1.0	1.5	2.2	2.7	6.9	14.1	4.1	7.1	6.9	4.1	6.0	17.7	17.4	10.0	9.9	6.9	5.9	5.5	4.4	5.5	0.6	1.5	3.3	6.3	
Rohru	5.2	8.6	9.6	2.4	4.5	3.2	1.3	3.2	1.6	2.4	5.6	4.2	12.2	8.3	15.3	21.2	18.6	14.3	24.8	22.5	19.7	30.6	15.1	17.6	22.2	16.1	14.1	13.0	16.1	13.4	13.4	
Salooni	19.8	18.6	35.5	17.6	21.8	28.7	28.8	28	18.2	66.7	25.1	33.0	52.8	63.7	48.4	46.9	22.9	32.7	51.4	29.0	22.9	38.0	17.3	34.2	37.0	23.0	20.2	18.1	35.2	13.9	21.2	
Sangla	17.5	11.0	17.6	9.7	10.2	6.4	5.3	6.9	6.4	6.3	4.8	9.1	7.8	12.2	16.0	13.6	18.8	32.2	16.2	16.7	25.2	17.5	21.6	16.2	9.5	21.5	16.8	23.4	16.7	15.8	11.5	
Sarkaghat	4.9	5.3	4.0	1.7	3.4	3.5	1.0	2.3	2.5	3.6	5.9	5.0	8.2	7.3	8.2	14.1	17.4	10.1	11.0	15.2	13.0	15.8	11.7	11.7	15.9	6.9	9.9	8.3	10.1	8.9	11.3	
Shimla	7.7	9.6	8.7	1.8	0.9	2.1	1.1	4.6	1.9	2.7	7.4	6.9	10.0	7.6	12.9	21.5	14.2	8.5	24.5	20.2	16.9	20.8	11.3	18.4	17.0	13.6	8.8	13.5	7.8	13.8	14.1	
Sundarnagar	22.4	13.0	7.3	11.8	9.0	5.5	6.5	8.3	6.0	2.7	4.9	6.1	7.2	8.7	10.1	8.2	24.5	17.5	9.6	15.9	18.9	18.8	22.8	13.6	19.0	9.3	15.3	10.4	10.9	10.3	11.4	
Theog	3.5	7.3	7.6	4.0	1.2	2.1	1.6	2.5	2.0	1.6	6.7	4.7	13.1	7.3	12.7	13.1	16.6	8.0	16.9	25.4	19.1	23.4	16.4	16.2	21.6	10.7	19.4	11.1	10.1	15.4	13.0	
Udaipur	6.4	8.3	8.6	8.8	2.3	3.8	2.4	1.6	1.0	4.0	5.1	15.2	5.5	20.5	18.5	20.6	10.6	14.2	46.4	25.8	18.5	28.4	21.7	12.0	25.0	12.9	14.0	14.6	14.7	15.9	9.0	
Una	6.0	5.0	3.8	1.2	0.8	3.3	2.3	4.6	5.4	0.9	5.2	7.4	9.4	6.6	9.1	10.1	12.8	7.5	8.8	19.8	11.2	10.0	9.2	11.4	6.9	6.7	3.5	6.2	5.5	5.1	8.8	
State	9.0	9.3	7.3	4.0	3.4	5.5	3.6	3.6	3.3	6.4	7.6	7.6	11.7	10.7	13.4	17.6	16.5	13.5	22.7	22.3	17.0	19.7	14.5	17.1	17.3	11.2	10.7	10.0	11.9	10.5	10.9	
SD	6.9	5.1	6.0	3.4	4.0	9.4	4.6	4.3	3.2	13.2	4.1	5.1	8.4	9.8	7.9	7.4	6.5	6.6	9.2	6.2	6.2	7.2	7.2	7.6	6.8	8.2	5.7	7.3	5.3	7.4	4.8	4.5
CV	76.7	54.5	81.6	86.6	118.1	170.5	126.2	120.2	97.1	206.0	53.7	67.5	72.1	91.5	59.1	41.7	39.5	48.8	40.4	27.8	36.3	36.5	52.5	39.7	47.5	50.9	68.5	53.1	61.9	45.7	41.4	

Annexure 1b

Normal weekly rainy days in different rapeseed-mustard growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Station	40	41	42	43	44	45	46	47	48	49	50	51	52	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18		
Akrot	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	
Arki	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Bajaura	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	
Banjar	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1		
Berthin	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	
Bhoranj	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	
Chachiot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1		
Dehra	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	
Dharamshala	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Dhaulakuan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	
Ghumarwin	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	
Hamirpur	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Jogindenagar	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	2	2	1	0	
Jubbal	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	
Kandaghat	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kangra	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Karsog	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kasuli	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Keylong	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kotkhai	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Kumarsain	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Malan	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	
Mandi	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	
Mashobra	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Nadaun	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0		
Nahan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1		
Nichar	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	
Nurpur	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	
Pachhad	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0		
Palampur	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Paunta	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	
Rohru	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	
Salooni	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1
Sangla	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Sarkaghat	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Shimla	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Sundarnagar	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Theog	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Udaipur	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Una	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1		
State	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	

Normal monthly temperature (°C) of different rapeseed-mustard growing environments of Himachal Pradesh

Month	Akrot		Bajaura		Berthin		Dhaulakuan		Kangra		Malan		Palampur		Salooni		Shimla		Mean	
	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min	Max	Min
October	30.9	16.4	27.4	9.0	29.3	14.1	29.7	13.7	28.8	15.8	27.3	15.0	24.8	13.6	25.4	13.6	21.2	11.5	27.2	13.6
November	26.8	10.8	23.3	3.5	25.4	7.3	25.9	8.0	24.8	10.0	24.0	10.8	21.1	9.5	23.4	11.9	17.8	8.3	23.6	8.9
December	22.2	7.0	18.2	0.7	20.9	4.0	21.9	4.5	20.9	6.2	19.9	7.3	17.6	6.4	20.2	10.1	14.6	5.6	19.6	5.8
January	19.2	6.1	15.9	1.0	18.6	3.6	19.5	4.4	18.3	5.2	16.9	5.7	15.2	4.9	18.0	8.1	12.1	3.6	17.1	4.7
February	22.1	9.1	17.5	3.4	21.3	6.5	22.3	6.5	20.2	8.2	18.9	7.2	16.6	6.4	16.5	7.0	13.2	4.4	18.7	6.5
March	28.0	12.8	21.9	6.0	27.0	9.4	27.5	10.0	25.7	10.7	23.7	10.1	20.9	10.1	19.2	8.0	17.3	7.9	23.5	9.4
April	34.5	17.9	26.4	9.1	31.9	12.9	33.8	14.0	30.9	15.0	28.6	13.5	26.1	14.5	20.1	8.3	21.7	12.1	28.2	13.0
May	37.8	22.6	30.4	12.7	35.6	17.4	36.9	19.0	34.6	18.5	33.2	18.2	29.9	18.2	21.1	9.0	25.0	15.6	31.6	16.8

Annexure 1d

Normal monthly rainfall (mm) of different rapeseed-mustard growing stations of Himachal Pradesh

Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Akrot	25	5	16	40	47	31	23	40	Kumarsain	18	13	23	51	61	57	45	57
Arki	25	12	28	56	66	62	32	48	Malan	26	13	22	70	82	58	30	36
Bajaura	26	19	34	67	105	114	70	73	Mandi	66	56	77	106	83	73	60	88
Banjar	20	16	30	67	86	95	60	65	Mashobra	53	16	30	79	111	88	62	88
Berthin	19	7	20	53	62	55	21	39	Nadaun	22	6	28	41	56	42	18	27
Bhoranj	17	4	15	58	68	50	27	57	Nahan	22	8	31	45	57	38	18	45
Chachiot	16	4	12	37	44	36	30	55	Nichar	16	19	28	110	113	124	78	74
Dehra	25	10	32	55	66	57	28	44	Nurpur	64	71	80	89	105	85	81	66
Dharamshala	43	19	47	93	113	112	60	72	Pachhad	25	11	31	51	66	52	33	34
Dhaulakuan	20	6	28	43	67	37	21	48	Palampur	34	19	45	97	105	108	56	81
Ghumarwin	29	14	26	67	72	58	31	40	Paonta	18	4	27	26	54	26	11	30
Hamirpur	29	13	29	65	81	63	35	55	Rohru	26	13	24	73	90	82	60	52
Jogindernagar	35	12	30	80	87	87	70	39	Salooni	98	115	182	198	135	133	95	66
Jubbal	35	11	37	77	78	83	56	83	Sangla	58	31	30	75	82	76	79	62
Kandaghat	28	13	42	56	75	56	30	44	Sarkaghat	17	11	23	53	50	55	40	61
Kangra	26	17	22	61	74	50	39	27	Shimla	28	10	27	60	76	70	47	69
Karsog	23	15	22	63	73	82	51	58	Sundarnagar	58	31	22	61	59	75	51	60
Kasauli	26	13	28	51	67	64	29	57	Theog	23	9	26	55	76	76	58	68
Keylong	13	17	36	43	78	106	57	38	Udaipur	32	11	30	71	111	93	61	45
Kotkhai	19	9	21	45	61	43	43	68	Una	16	16	23	43	47	40	21	29
Over all mean										30	18	34	66	77	70	45	55
Stan. Dev										17	20	27	29	21	27	20	17
CV (%)										57	113	81	43	28	38	45	31

Annexure 1e

Normal monthly rainy days of different rapeseed-mustard growing stations of Himachal Pradesh

Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Station	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May
Akrot	2	1	1	3	3	3	2	3	Kumarsain	2	1	2	4	5	5	5	5
Arki	1	1	2	3	5	4	3	3	Malan	2	1	2	4	6	5	3	3
Bajaura	2	2	2	4	7	7	6	6	Mandi	4	3	4	6	6	6	5	6
Banjar	2	2	2	5	6	7	6	7	Mashobra	4	2	2	5	6	7	6	7
Berthin	2	1	1	3	4	4	2	3	Nadaun	1	1	1	3	4	3	2	2
Bhoranj	1	0	1	4	4	3	2	3	Nahan	1	1	2	3	4	3	1	3
Chachiot	0	0	1	2	3	2	2	3	Nichar	2	2	2	5	7	8	6	7
Dehra	2	1	2	4	4	4	2	3	Nurpur	4	4	5	5	5	5	5	4
Dharamshala	3	2	3	6	6	7	5	5	Pachhad	1	1	2	3	4	3	2	2
Dhaulakuan	1	1	1	3	4	3	2	4	Palampur	2	1	2	5	6	6	4	5
Ghumarwin	2	1	1	4	4	4	2	3	Paonta	1	0	2	2	3	2	1	3
Hamirpur	2	1	2	4	6	5	3	5	Rohru	2	1	2	5	6	6	5	5
Jogindernagar	2	1	2	5	6	5	5	3	Salooni	4	5	6	6	6	5	5	4
Jubbal	2	1	3	5	6	7	5	7	Sangla	5	4	3	4	4	5	5	6
Kandaghat	2	1	2	4	5	4	3	4	Sarkaghat	2	1	2	4	4	4	3	5
Kangra	3	1	2	4	5	4	3	3	Shimla	2	1	2	4	5	5	4	6
Karsog	2	1	2	4	5	6	4	5	Sundarnagar	4	3	2	4	4	5	4	4
Kasuli	2	1	2	3	5	4	3	4	Theog	1	1	2	4	5	6	5	5
Keylong	1	2	3	3	5	6	5	4	Udaipur	4	2	3	4	6	6	5	5
Kotkhai	1	1	2	4	5	4	4	6	Una	1	1	1	3	3	3	2	2
									Over all mean	2	1	2	4	5	5	4	4
									Stan. Dev	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
									CV (%)	53	72	46	25	21	31	41	33

Crop Management

a. Weather based management of rapeseed-mustard crop in rapeseed-mustard growing environments

Weather parameters (particularly, ambient temperature, rainfall and sunshine etc.,) bear a direct relationship with germination, growth and development of different crops. The anticipated regime of different weather parameters is decided by weather forecast. The weather forecast is not only useful for sowing, growth, development, harvesting, threshing and other management practices but also for application of various agrochemicals for control of insect pest and weeds. For example, the sowing of crops can commence with the improvement of ambient and soil temperature in extremely cold/hot areas and also with increased soil moisture in dry areas. Soil temperature of surface and first few centimeters underneath, determines the germination and emergence of the seeds. No germination takes place under the availability of scarce soil moisture and extremely low/high temperature conditions. Hence, weather based management plays an extremely useful role in managing weather vagaries and capitalizing benevolent effect of weather for increasing the production and productivity of all crops including rapeseed-mustard. The application of agrochemicals is effective only if the sky is clear (<1 mm daily rainfall) and adequate soil moisture (20-30%) is present in the soil. Higher wind speed more than 8 kmph drifts the agrochemicals away from the target and reduces the efficacy of these chemicals considerably. At the time of sowing or within few days of sowing adequate soil moisture must be present in the soil for proper germination. With upper soil surface well pulverized, occurrence of 10 mm of rain generally wets soil depth up to 25-30cm. With occurrence of 10 mm of rainfall decision can be taken whether sowing can be commenced or not. Field operations involving manual labour should also be guided through weather forecast as it will improve the efficiency of the farm operations at one hand and reduce the wasteful labour cost induced by malevolent weather on the other. The application of the weather forecast can thus, really prove useful for increasing the yield of different crops by reducing the cost of cultivation in different crops.

b. Management before and during sowing, and after germination

For uniform germination and adequate crop stand rapeseed-mustard crops require a well pulverized and compact seed-bed. To attain desirable seed-bed where rice is grown as upland or transplanted crop, 2-3 ploughings, repeated harrowings, cultivation and planking or laddering are required for raising a good crop. However, in well-drained loamy, sandy loam and clayey loam soils only 1-2 ploughings, one harrowing, cultivation and planking might be sufficient. Breaking of clods in clayey loam or silty loam soil is a very difficult as criss-cross mechanical tillage/ploughings is not feasible in small and terraced fields. In that case, a clod breaker, an implement called as '*Bhutann*' (which is one foot long cylindrical strong wooden log with pointed end meant for digging the buried clods and flat from the other to crush/break the clods, with a long strong wooden handle) in Palam valley is used to break the clods.

Under rain fed conditions, cultivation of rapeseed-mustard is difficult though other climatic/weather conditions are favourable for its growth. For management of soil moisture for ensuring proper germination, the residual moisture available in the soil after receding the monsoon is conserved through proper tillage and planking to ensure sufficient seed-soil contact. The experienced farmers also harvest/capture dew by ploughing and seeding the crop in the evening and planking the same in the early morning. Though remains higher than ambient, the soil temperatures, fall rapidly during winter. Soil temperature is also highly variable in different parts of the state due to its varied topography and geographical settings. Under very low ambient temperature germination of rapeseed-mustard crop is hampered. The early sowing is thus, has an over-riding advantage of utilizing the residual soil moisture and optimum soil temperature for ensuring proper germination.

Sowing is a major operation for cultivation of rapeseed-mustard. Placing the seeds at proper depth into a soil of proper tilth is called as seeding. It involves selection of varieties, time of seeding, seed rate, method of seeding, seeding depth, spacing etc. Sowing time is the foremost non-monetary input determining the productivity to a greater extent. In most of the states, under normal conditions the row to row and plant to plant spacing of 45x15 cm is optimum (Rathore and Kumpawat, 1992). Delay in planting/sowing generally tends to give lower yields of seed as well as oil which may primarily be due to shorter duration of reproductive phase, thus allowing less time for formation of siliquae and development of seeds. In such cases the protein content in seeds were found to be higher. In early planting, the maximum and minimum temperature during

vegetative phase are considerably higher. The maximum temperature of the vegetative phase bears a positive and significant correlation with seed yield. Planting of mustard during first week of October, recorded significantly higher seed yields and one month delay in sowing reduced the seed yield to the extent of about 45% (Shastry and Kumar, 1981). At Palampur in gobhi sarson, with every 10 days delay in planting from 20th October, the reduction in seed yield was found to be 8.8 and 19.6 %, respectively with overall reduction of 26.7% up to 10th November in 20 days delay in planting (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of sowing time on yield attributes, 1000-seed weight and seed yield of gobhi sarson at Palampur

Sowing time	No. of branches/plant	No. of siliquae/plant	1000- seed wt. (g)	Seed yield (kg/ha)
20 th October	11.7	85.8	4.12	1709
30 th October	12.5	79.1	3.89	1558
10 th November	13.2	70.5	3.76	1253

Establishment of optimum plant stand is a real bottleneck in realization of good harvest. To obtain proper crop stand and good seed yield, line sowing is must. Optimum plant population is maintained through thinning after 10-15 days of sowing under irrigated condition and 15-20 days under rain fed condition and simultaneously intercultural operation carried out which enables individual plant to branch profusely, utilize the available nutrients, space, light, remove weeds and conserve soil moisture effectively. Thinning, will thus, reduce plant density and will lower inter- plant competition.

c. Varieties

The production of rapeseed-mustard could be increased to a greater extent, as the present day varieties are capable of yielding up to 30q/ha. For raising good crop of rapeseed-mustard only recommended varieties given in the package and practices of CSK HPKV should be grown. For further details the package and practices for *rabi* crops of CSK HPKV should be consulted (www.hillagric.ac.in). In present investigation five varieties GSL-1, HPN-1, HPN-3, Hyola-401 and ONK-1 belonging to gobhi sarson group were used. These high yielding varieties of gobhi sarson, have the inherent ability to stabilize the yield at higher level under varied agro climatic conditions of Himachal Pradesh. Besides its high yielding ability, it has an edge over the best

national, zonal and state checks for oil yield, percent oil content, maturity duration and resistance to various diseases. The varietal characteristics of these varieties are given below:

Varietal Characteristics:

Key varietal parameters	Name of varieties				
	GSL-1	HPN-1	HPN-3	Hyola-401	ONK-1
Type of cultivar	National check	Local check	Local check	Hybrid	Local check
Days to maturity	150-160	175-180	160-165	150-155	145-185
Plant height (cm)	170-180	170-175	160-165	124-135	132-186
Suitable sowing time	Early sowing	Timely and late sowing	Timely and late sowing	Timely sowing	Early sowing

d. Fertilizer applications

Rapeseed- mustard is also an exhaustive crop. A study on the assessment of contribution of various agronomic inputs on performance of Indian mustard revealed fertilizer as most critical input under mid-hill conditions of Himachal Pradesh. Fertilizers contributes 37 to 75% of the increase in yield which can be brought about by adoption of full package of practices. Mustard crop yielding about 26 q/ha, absorb approximately 131 kg N, 26 kg phosphorous and 133 kg potassium and 12 kg Sulphur (Thakur *et. al.*, 2007). Until and unless these nutrients are replenished, the soil remains depleted and crop suffers acutely, resulting in poor productivity of the crop.

Application of fertilizer in right amount, place and time enhances crop yield remarkably. Complete dose of phosphate, potash, sulphur and half of nitrogen should be given at the time of sowing through line sowing or *pora* method. The remaining half dose of nitrogen should be applied before flowering if sufficient soil moisture is available or it should be applied after irrigation wherever irrigation facilities exist. In case of gobhi sarson, full dose of phosphate, potash and half of nitrogen should be given at the time of sowing. Each half of the remaining dose of nitrogen should be applied respectively at 60 days and 80-90 days after sowing before flowering.

The crop yield increased significantly with increase in nitrogen levels. The response to nitrogen application has been obtained up to 120 kg N/ha. Application of phosphorus is more effective when combined with nitrogen and potassium. The interaction between nitrogen and sulphur has been positive and significant for seed yield as well as for nutrient content. Combined use of phosphorus and sulphur also produced a synergistic effect on the yield of rain fed mustard

(Singh *et. al.*, 1983). Since, sulphur is directly involved in oil synthesis and is a constituent of mustard oil (glucosides and glucosinolates), effect of sulphur on oil content is often positive. An increase up to 60% in oil content has been observed by sulphur application.

To get the complete benefit of nitrogen it should be applied at adequate soil moisture or after adequate rain/ irrigation. Therefore, the application of nitrogen should be planned and applied taking medium range forecast into consideration, if no rain is expected in next 3-5 days only then nitrogen in the form of urea should be applied otherwise severe leaching losses are imminent.

e. Irrigation management

Generally rapeseed-mustard group of crops are grown with wheat as an intercrop or a mixed crop or as a sole crop. Irrigation applied to the main wheat crop is generally sufficient for these crops. In case of sole crop, pre-sowing irrigation must be applied to ensure germination. Generally, this crop requires no irrigation, if one or two rains are received during winter season. Wherever irrigation facilities are available apply one irrigation in 'Raya' crop at 75 per cent flowering stage. Over irrigation and heavy rainfall in heavier soil are undesirable as rapeseed-mustard cannot tolerate waterlogged conditions.

f. Weeds management

Weeds, the unwanted plants do not cause heavy losses to rapeseed-mustard crop. Weeds can cause maximum damage during early crop growth stages. When crop is three weeks old hoeing and thinning must be done to ensure 10-15cm plant to plant spacing. Manual weeding in 'Raya' must be done at 30 and 60 days and in gobhi sarson at 40 and 70 days after sowing. Manual weeding, is the best for the production of higher yield, but it is very costly, labourious, tedious and time consuming. Therefore, for commercial cultivation it may not be feasible. The crop should be kept weed- free, only by using recommended pre or post emergence herbicides. Use of herbicides has become quite prevalent in several parts of the country, since it is economical, effective and enables timely control of weeds. Recommended doses of herbicides should be applied for higher yields. Spray should be planned and applied taking medium range forecast in to considerations.

g. Management of weather aberrations during different phenophases

To ensure good germination and early seedling vigour, seeds should be soaked in water before sowing, if adequate soil moisture is not available under rain fed conditions (Rathore and Kumapawat, 1992). This is best done by soaking the seeds in gunny bag or cover the gunny bag with seeds directly with damp earth for overnight.

Rapeseed-mustard does not tolerate water logging conditions therefore, irrigation must be applied only after taking weather forecast into consideration. In the event of untimely heavy rainfall after irrigation or heavy rainfall per se in heavy soils, proper drainage must be ensured during all the phenophases of the crop.

Both advective and radiational frosts occur in Himachal Pradesh but their intensity does not cause considerable losses in rapeseed-mustard. An analysis of screen temperature records for the years 2001-02 to 2015-16 of Agrometeorological observatory, CSKHPKV, Palampur revealed that frost events are highly variable from year to year. Frosts are generally few in the month of December, common in January especially the second half of this month and rare after mid-February. Frost days during years 2007-08 to 2015-16 are presented in Fig. 1. Three (2009-10 to 2011-12) years in a row experienced higher frost events. The highest number of events (24) observed during 2011 followed by 18 and 17 during 2005 and 2013, respectively.

The frosty and cloudy weather conditions during flowering, siliquae formation and seed filling phase are quite harmful which not only adversely affect honeybee activity but also cause heavy damage to seeds at intermediate stage of development of *B. juncea* (Dhawan, 1985). The yield reductions are more due to frosty weather in *B. campestris* than *B. juncea*. Frost tolerance depend upon the species of rapeseed-mustard viz., taramira is most frost tolerant (93.3%) followed by yellow sarson (60.6%), brown sarson (51.1%) and Indian mustard (41.8%) (Kumar and Yadav, 1992). The management of frost is best done before sowing/onset of the frost, therefore it is suggested that the selection of species must be carefully done in accordance with their frost tolerance limits and frequency of occurrence of frost.

Time of harvesting of crop considerably influence the seed yield as well as the quality of seed. Premature harvesting, however, causes respiration losses, resulting in lower yield and poor oil content as well as well as poor seed viability. Delay in harvesting might result in seed losses due to shattering in rapeseed. Rapeseed-mustard should therefore be harvested when 75% of the

siliquae turns yellow, as there is no increase in seed yield and oil content after this stage in most of varieties. The crop should also be preferably harvested in the morning hours when the siliquae are damp with dew which will help to reduce shattering losses. Heavy rainfall accompanied with storm could cause heavy losses in harvested and standing crop, hence harvesting must be undertaken in a clear weather after taking weather forecast into consideration.

After harvesting, the crop should be stacked in heaps for curing for 4-5 days till the seeds turned brown. The heaps should be kept covered with a cloth/gunny bags during curing.

Fig. 1 Frost days during years 2007-08 to 2015-16. Each dot indicates date on which observed. Height of the dot indicates screen temperature and figures on x-axis show year and dates of the month

Annexure 3

Phenophase-wise accumulated photo-thermal units (PTU) taken by different rapeseed-mustard varieties

Phenological stage/sowing date	Accumulated photo-thermal units		
	20 th October	30 th October	10 th November
GSL-1			
Emergence	1341	1562	1179
First flower	7927	7839	7195
50% flowering	9592	8989	8185
90% siliquae filling	15391	14371	13174
Physiological maturity	18497	17033	16147
HPN-1			
Emergence	1173	1602	1427
First flower	7881	7951	7180
50% flowering	9784	9024	8536
90% siliquae filling	13951	13554	12152
Physiological maturity	19127	18414	17190
HPN-3			
Emergence	1144	1597	1521
First flower	7907	7875	7059
50% flowering	9946	9020	8545
90% siliquae filling	13777	12835	12280
Physiological maturity	19098	18391	17444
Hyola-401			
Emergence	1243	1657	1438
First flower	7803	7652	7165
50% flowering	9835	9375	8164
90% siliquae filling	13678	12337	12504
Physiological maturity	19027	18471	17805
ONK-1			
Emergence	1545	1593	1182
First flower	7671	7890	7122
50% flowering	9486	9185	8269
90% siliquae filling	15216	14559	13407
Physiological maturity	18049	17405	16204
Pooled			
Emergence	1289	1602	1349
First flower	7838	7841	7144
50% flowering	9729	9119	8340
90% siliquae filling	14403	13531	12703
Physiological maturity	18760	17943	16958

Annexure 3a

Phenophase-wise accumulative helio-thermal units (HTU) taken by different rapeseed-mustard varieties

Phenological stage/sowing date	Accumulated helio-thermal units		
	20 th October	30 th October	10 th November
GSL-1			
Emergence	1036	1165	1025
First flower	5979	5693	5036
50% flowering	7023	6287	5585
90% siliquae filling	10009	9174	8236
Physiological maturity	11832	10667	10059
HPN-1			
Emergence	897	1233	1131
First flower	5949	5790	4995
50% flowering	7151	6303	5703
90% siliquae filling	9215	8736	7690
Physiological maturity	12282	11687	10700
HPN-3			
Emergence	868	1231	1202
First flower	5176	5756	4935
50% flowering	7177	6327	5703
90% siliquae filling	9141	8313	7709
Physiological maturity	12245	11669	10919
Hyola-401			
Emergence	960	1251	1135
First flower	5902	5597	4984
50% flowering	7124	6492	5496
90% siliquae filling	9078	7995	7866
Physiological maturity	12216	11725	11090
ONK-1			
Emergence	1174	1193	1027
First flower	5783	5727	4979
50% flowering	6961	6425	5625
90% siliquae filling	9888	9313	8398
Physiological maturity	11508	10922	10098
Pooled			
Emergence	987	1215	1104
First flower	5758	5712	4986
50% flowering	7087	6367	5622
90% siliquae filling	9466	8706	7980
Physiological maturity	12016	11334	10573

